

University of Essex
**Dept of Computer Science and
Electrical Engineering**

MSc Cyber Security: Capstone Project Dissertation

Security Event Log Deidentification

A Security Analyst Training and Intrusion Detection Research
Solution

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Abstract

This thesis explores a programmatic method for deidentifying organizational cyber event data into functional training sets suitable for cyber security research and skills development. A 4-phase methodology was developed to support repeatable extraction, deidentification and replacement of sensitive values such as IP addresses, computer, domain, and account names. A proof-of concept was implemented via software modules integrated into a customized Logstash pipeline deidentifying data inline to create replica logfiles.

Record formats and content variance necessitated multiple parsing approaches enforced by conditional software logic because ad-hoc search and replace proved inadequate for privacy preservation or reliably formatted output. The second finding reaffirmed the privacy-utility continuum, I.E., reidentification risk should be weighed against the opportunity costs of not supporting cyber security and observability research data needs.

Testing in a corporate network lab replica generating more than 100,000 events per day confirmed Windows, Linux, and firewall event data deidentification at 130 to 200+ events per second with cyber intrusion data successfully identified in an Elasticsearch analytics platform. Next steps are cyber specialist field testing to determine the viability of threat hunting and detection engineering using deidentified data.

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis presented for the degree of MSc Cyber Security has been composed solely by myself, it has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification. Except where stated otherwise by reference or acknowledgement, the work presented is entirely my own.

Douglas Leece

April 2023

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Introduction

Problem Overview and Project Motivation

As devices and people in the world continue to digitally interconnect the consequences of cyber-based attacks increase in significance with impacts experienced financially, kinetically, and physiologically (Borwell et al., 2021; Humayun et al., 2021). Metaphors like “data as currency” or “the new oil” may now appear hyperbolic (Nolin, 2020; OECD, 2015) but there appears to be consistent agreement amongst academics and industry that identifying and mitigating digitization threats must continue and there are significant gaps in our detection and defense capabilities.

The world’s first personal banking terminal and first smart phone may appear comical to some, (fig 1.1, fig 1.2), until considering a small portion of the global commercial airline fleet operate daily with planes of similar and older vintage (JETechnology, 2021). Unlike the aviation industry’s strong history of improvements in technology, training, regulation, and safety that began shortly after the Wright brothers (FAA, n.d.), the fourth industrial revolution has wider direct impacts to people and the planet, less scrutiny, and a much greater change velocity (Xu, X. et al., 2021).

Figure 1.1 Bank of Scotland "Homelink" 1983 (Finextra, 2013)

Figure 1.2 IBM Simon 1994 (Tocci, 2023)

Despite Industry 4.0 being usurped in 2021 by the European Commission’s declaration of a fifth industrial revolution (EC, n.d.) core messages regarding digital transformation and workforce skills have not changed. Realizing digitization benefits individually or organizationally depends on critical infrastructure resilience. Although several pages of the OECD 2015 Data Innovation Report argue for data as infrastructure, (OECD, 2015), citing Frischmann’s societal value of shared infrastructure (Frischmann, 2012) multiple times, a 2023 World Economic Forum panel on securing critical infrastructure confirmed this is a hard problem not yet solved. Multiple panel experts stated governments and industry collaboration was required and workforce competency must be a priority (WEF, 2023).

Workers and contextual understanding are both requirements, cyber-attack detection and response is complex because organizations differ, threat types differ and quickly evolve. The CyBOK knowledge Area Security Operations and Incident Management (SOIM) (Rashid et al., 2021) provides an overview of some technological and operational requirements for response capability, identifying many technological inputs (fig 1.3) but failing to highlight effective identification and response being highly reliant on data analysis. Unfortunately, most organizations struggle to address the analysis function (Givens, 2019), something this project endeavours to contribute toward resolving.

Figure 1.3 MAPE-K Autonomic computing loop instantiated to SOIM (Rashid et al, 2019)

Workforce Gaps

Multiple factors contribute to the cybersecurity workforce shortage issues, beginning with raw numbers of viable workforce candidates. The Cyber Incident Responder/Analyst role defined by European, and U.S. cyber work force development agencies requires extensive technical understanding of networking, operating systems, applications, and log file analysis (ENISA, 2023; NICCS, n.d.) yet organizations report 35-60% of their employees struggle with general ICT skills (ECORYS UK, 2016).

Organizations such as ENISA and NICCS have defined competencies for highly skilled ICT roles and policy makers recognizing the issue drive government initiatives funding training (ECORYS UK, 2016; GoC, 2023) to create viable workers but delivery remains with educational institutions. The UK Digital Skills Report (2016) identified less than half of secondary school ICT instructors had qualifications in the field and 60% felt unprepared to deliver the curriculum. At higher levels institutions are typically tasked with making training accessible to many levels with limited resources and short time frames and face significant scrutiny on value (Meyer, 2023) which may be warranted. A case study reviewing a three-credit university cybersecurity course curriculum identified the practical element was querying a website's API with python and cross-referencing a vulnerability database (Fernández-Caramés & Fraga-Lamas, 2020). Course

completion would provide limited benefit to an industrial automation cybersecurity analyst, yet high success metrics were awarded for student satisfaction, not job readiness.

The apparent shortfalls within education are reflected in Blazic’s 2021 European ICT workforce study which reported more than 30% of failed hires were due to skills mismatch, again claiming higher education institutions are not providing current curriculum or hands-on training to address the gap (Dragoni et al., 2021; ECORYS UK, 2016). Sandia National Laboratories, addressing the U.S. Department of Homeland Security (Urias et al., 2017), reported a similar skills concern with industrial defense. Calls for more practical hands-on training including the use of cyber ranges (NIST, 2018), may be loud and clear, but effectiveness determination is up to the organization using the range, something education institutions can not do in a vacuum.

Both the Sandia authors and Blazic’s European ICT workforce requirements analysis further assert realistic simulations, specific to the industry vertical are essential for analyst competency development. Figure 1.4 illustrates skill requirements are similarly named but priority ratios differ considerably between verticals. Each industry also requires specific forms of training data, a quandary was articulated in a 2010 seminal paper on the use of machine learning for intrusion detection within network traffic.

“...specifics of the problem domain...(iv) the enormous variability of benign traffic, making it difficult to find stable notions of normality...” (Sommer & Paxson, 2010)

Figure 1.4 Technology areas where cybersecurity skills are most needed identified by the participating EU industry sectors (Blazič,2021)Data Sharing

Data Sharing Requirements

While cyber ranges are effective training aids, realistic simulations require effort to build and maintain (Chouliaras et al., 2021; NIST cyber range guide). This maintenance extends beyond the technology underlying the cyber range to the actual data observed or generated within the range. Revisiting network intrusion detection via machine learning a decade later, (Nazir &

Khan, R. A., 2021) reach similar conclusions to Sommer and Paxon (2010), calling for mechanisms to access new cyber event datasets quickly to best identify emerging threats.

Repeated requests from respected researchers for industry or organizationally specific data, begins to make sense when the current state of data collection is considered. Observable cyber event artifacts such as account, computer and domain names, IP addresses, active processes and so forth are recorded in the same way for both benign/normal and malicious activity. Differentiating malicious from normal requires the mental context of an analyst, or machine learning modelled after an analyst. Post secondary can certainly provide generalized computer security training but often lacks industry specific cyber event data and contextual knowledge to fully educate the analyst.

Ironically the specific cyber event data required for training is plentiful in most organizations since regulatory requirements often mandate collection and analysis for potential intrusions as well as long term retention for compliance (European Commission, 2010; NERC, 2022; PCI SSC, 2022). Data sharing between organizations already collecting and educational facilities training workers for these organizations initially appears logical. Unfortunately, this same data is also considered confidential because it can disclose system vulnerabilities (Rodríguez-Hoyos et al., 2019) or be used to identify individual behaviours (Tudor et al., 2015). Consequently, despite the need, cyber event data should not be made available in its original state for public research or released in a controlled manner such as a partnership with an educational institution.

Data Sharing Obstacles

Industry providing data for research education is not new and guidelines exist on how to protect sensitive information in the dataset (AEPD, 2021; Cavoukian & Castro, 2014; Garfinkel, S. L., 2015).

While the term “anonymization” is often used, the correct term is normally “deidentification” since reidentification may be possible given enough time and effort (Barbaro & Zeller, 2006; Coull et al., 2009; Narayanan & Felten, E., 2019; Sweeney, 1997). Healthcare or financial records are typically independent or atomic in nature but linkage between quasi-identifiers within different event log sources must be maintained for cybersecurity investigations that rely on correlation and timeline analysis. Event field values cannot simply be randomized and maintain the required temporal relationships needed for analysis (Lee, 2012; Pang et al, 2006; Qardaji & Li, 2012).

Often referred to as quasi-identifiers, IP addresses, computer host or account names do not directly identify a specific individual but aggregate analysis and linking with other data can lead to identification (Garfinkel, S. L., 2015; Ohm, 2010; Sweeney, 1997). Although Sweeney and Ohm were primarily focused on personal health care records, GDPR article 11 and 4 require that electronic identifiers like account names or IP addresses within datasets available to processors must not reidentify individuals (GDPR, 2018a; Hintze, 2018).

The format of the deidentified cyber event data must also be maintained for human analysts and machine learning systems, figure 1.5 illustrates the need for syntactically correct data while maintaining privacy. In this example, the technician requires sample data to assist, and data value correctness is secondary to log format correctness.

Figure 1.5 Technical Support Posting

Following this line of logic, a third-party data processor (3DP) may only need to examine the behaviour of network traffic, not the specific individual hosts involved, a similar looking IP address may suffice. This is premise of prefix preserving IP deidentification solutions (Pang et al., 2006; Xu, J. et al., 2001; Zhang et al., 2006), a similar concept would be used in this project using shift cipher encryption.

Solution Overview

To balance privacy and utility this research project developed a cipher algorithm to modify the true values of IP addresses and network source ports while retaining realistic data values suitable for human pattern recognition, database indexing and searching. Sensitive text-based field data was pseudonymized using format preserving encryption (FPE) for the same reasons. Privacy for sensitive field values was achieved using a key set applied to the cipher and FPE processes with key value secrecy maintained by the organization. Protecting key sets is less logistically challenging than storing several million pseudonym tokens mapped to original data values to enable reidentification. When reidentification is required the 3DP need only provide the deidentified records to the original data owners (ODO) who have access to the secret key set decrypt the pseudonymized values.

Crypto analysts may point out symmetric ciphers are weaker than asymmetric key encryption since they are reversible by trying all possible values of the symmetric key, therefore any pseudonymization scheme reliant on a known cipher algorithm can ultimately be reversed as well (Garfinkel, S. L., 2015). The caveat to this concern is threat agents must also be in possession of known ciphertext as proven by luminary mathematicians Marian Rejewski and Alan Turing who defeated Enigma machine cryptography due to regular inclusion of certain phrases in the messages (Copeland, 2010). To address this potential threat, well known accounts like “root” and “administrator” and IP addresses like “127.0.0.1” are intentionally excluded from encryption. Chapter four includes a complete description of the

pseudonymization approach taken for both numeric data like IP addresses and source ports as well as text based sensitive information such as computer hostnames, account usernames, and file directory names. A risk assessment specifically on reidentification threats is also included in Appendix E.

Research Question

Revisiting an opening assertion, skill set development is often dependant on presenting realistic training environments for an analyst to work though and be tested on because malicious events are typically indistinguishable from normal usage until the data is viewed in aggregate. Analysis of the workforce gaps and data requirements for effective training resulted in the following research question and testable hypothesis:

What event log data must be deidentified to prevent identification of people or critical systems within the resulting dataset output when viewed within the intended analysis tools while simultaneously enabling intrusion investigation?

Hypothesis

Cyber event log data can be sufficiently deidentified to prevent reidentification from quasi-identifiers viewed within the intended analysis tool and be resistant to offline reidentification attacks within acceptable limits while simultaneously enabling the investigation and identification of potential cyber security events.

Contribution

The Security Event Log Deidentification (SELD) project has delivered a proof-of-concept software solution that can programmatically deidentify cyber event log records creating pseudonymized log files suitable for importing into security event analysis programs. This contribution is one approach to resolving a seemingly circular dilemma identified in the cybersecurity training of human analysts and machine learning models, summarized as follows:

- Cybersecurity skill shortages are particularly acute for security analysts (Givens, 2019),
- Practical analyst skill development requires industry specific event data presented in an event analysis platform (Blažič, 2021),
- Industries requiring analysts possess the data to populate such platforms have avoided sharing for decades due to privacy concerns (Xu, J. et al., 2001) and now face regulation (Hintze, 2018),
- Privacy mitigation via data deidentification is complicated by the need to maintain event temporal relationships and record realism (Lee, R., 2012; Portillo-Dominguez & Ayala-Rivera, 2019) because intrusion detection, either human or machine learning, relies on patterns (Ho et al., 2021; Sommer & Paxson, 2010)

The literature confirms balancing privacy with utility (Cavoukian & Castro, 2014; Hintze, 2018; Ohm, 2010; Sweeney, 1997) will continue factoring into data sharing conversations. European privacy law has been attempting to regulate this balance in relation to online electronic identities, similar to the record data analyzed in this project, placing limits on reidentification protection measures, including measures that destroy the intended function of the data (Article 29 Working Party, 2018). This project has taken a similar approach, presuming organizations most likely to benefit from advanced cyber security research and a deeper pool of competent analysts have risk management programs.

Related Work

An insight from data privacy research early in the project led to refactoring, specifically cyber event log records can not be fully anonymized and provide adequate input into the cybersecurity investigation process (DeYoung, 2018; Pang et al., 2006; Qardaji & Li, 2012; Rasic, 2020). The term “anonymized”, as related to data sharing, means original data subjects can not be reassociated with the shared anonymized data. Orthogonally, deidentification does not contain directly identifiable data but acknowledges reassociation through links with external datasets is always a possibility (Garfinkel, S. L., 2015; GDPR, 2018c; Narayanan et al., 2016). Both terms are used interchangeably throughout the literature, therefore used as search keywords but considered as deidentification during analysis.

Laboratory Environment Development

CyBOK knowledge area eight (Rashid et al., 2021), *Security Operations and Incident Management* (SOIM), covers many topics including log source descriptions, detection models, threat intelligence and incident response. Thirty-six pages allocated to this knowledge area briefly explain key concepts and items to consider if developing a security operations center but provide little information on how various functions interact within SOIM. In fairness to the author, entire books are written about each concept introduced in the SOIM knowledge area, therefore the CyBOK guide is an overview rather than design for security monitoring. MITRE’s World Class Strategies of CSOC 2nd edition (Knerler et al., 2022) provides excellent foundational guidance to determine functional and governance requirements for an effective SOIM capability but limiting technical guidance to architectural recommendations for defensible cyber event log collection within an organization’s live network, excessive for a lab design.

Building and maintaining organization-wide infrastructure for cyber event log collection, detection and analysis often requires several full-time employees (Knerler et al., 2022; Murdoch, 2018). Therefore, it is not surprising that replicating the computer systems and activities observed in a large organization for testing purposes, often called a cyber range, still represents considerable effort and most are purpose-built with limited scope. (Chouliaras et al., 2021) analyze twenty-five cyber ranges and training or research work they were designed to support, indicating most ranges were associated with military or academic organizations rather than opensource offerings suitable for extension into this project.

Some cyber security testing books provide guidance on lab building (Bodungen et al., 2016; Smith, 2021) to practice attack techniques but *The practice of Network Security Monitoring* (Bejtlich, 2013) is the rare publication providing design guidance event monitoring and collection in a lab environment. Though the lab instructions are technically dated, Bejtlich’s methodology for testing, attacking, and monitoring within the remainder of the book stands the test of time. Like Bejtlich, *The Blue Team Handbook, SOC, SIEM and Threat Hunting Use Cases* (Murdoch, 2018) focuses on detection of cyber attacks and implementation of detection solutions, although the author assumes investigations take place in an existing live environment and does not delve into lab development.

Research did not identify any regulatory standards for cyber ranges but simulating computer systems, network ranges and user activity in a representative environment for the threat scenario was a consistent theme (Furfaro et al., 2017; Somarakis et al., 2020; Urias et al., 2017). To support future research or validation testing, the project's lab design is detailed in appendix A.

Privacy Research

The CyBOK privacy and online rights knowledge area (Rashid et al., 2021) considers three privacy design paradigms:

- Confidentiality provided through various technical approaches,
- Control via data handling agreement,
- Transparency in the form of user awareness regarding data collection.

Like SOIM, the privacy knowledge area skims a wide surface area but does include obfuscation-based inference control as a technical confidentiality protection approach. Obfuscation measures appear to be the best path toward this project's data confidentiality and utility goals, an approach taken by many previous projects sharing network trace data for third party assessment (Mivule & Anderson, 2015; Mohammady et al., 2018; Pang et al., 2006; Xu, J. et al., 2001) and more recent research protecting personally identifiable information (PII) in other types of cyber event logs (DeYoung, 2018; Menges et al., 2021; Rasic, 2020).

(Fung et al., 2010), released a survey of obfuscation-based research focused on data subject privacy preservation while retaining a high degree of utility within published datasets in addition to expanding on many techniques discussed in CyBOK. The survey explains privacy preserving data publishing (PPDP) approaches and effectiveness measurement in-depth. Like many other researchers, Fung et al use examples of medical, census or financial record to illustrate deidentification concepts. Unfortunately, when applying such techniques to cybersecurity event logs the resulting dataset is not suitable for intrusion analysis (DeYoung, 2018; Menges et al., 2021; Rasic, 2020).

In earlier research (Samarati & Sweeney, 1998) recognized reidentification using indirect or quasi-identifiers such as zip code, gender or date of birth remained possible after direct identifiers like name or social insurance number were removed or masked. The authors proposed the concept of K-Anonymity, I.E., reducing precision in certain quasi-identifiers or suppressing unique records until a person can be associated with no less than " K " number of people. Generalization measures like changing birth date to year of birth do little to distort other valuable data in a medical record but will not work for cyber event record analysis. Analysts often search event data for patterns such as connections between specific computer hosts or multiple authentication failures for a specific account to identify security issues (Ho et al., 2021; Khan, S. & Parkinson, 2019; Vaarandi et al., 2016), relying on complete records with precise quasi-identifiers, something k-anonymity endeavours to prevent. Further to this point, actual intrusion event volume is typically orders of magnitude lower than benign traffic (Sommer & Paxson, 2010), removing outliers to meet k-anonymity requirements would remove the very evidence analysts should be training to find.

Synthetic contextual data or “dummy addition” approaches to obscure valid records (Fung et al., 2010; Rashid et al., 2021) confound event frequency-based detections and creation of convincingly realistic fake data is not trivial (Chow & Golle, 2009; Toemmel, 2021). Finally, obfuscation via perturbation techniques like random noise or data shuffling (Yancey et al., 2002) prevents accurate clustering analysis that relies on precise and consistent values within event records such as username, event outcome or IP address (Khan, S. & Parkinson, 2019; Wurzenberger et al., 2020).

Protecting IP address privacy within network traces has been ongoing research for decades (Meiss et al., 2007; Xu, J. et al., 2001) with most original solutions focused on replacing IP addresses while retaining routing characteristics within the records. Pang et al., (2006) determined more nuanced fields like TCP timestamps could also be used for reidentifying internal hosts and services, recommending risk analysis on information disclosed rather than dismiss the deidentification solution outright.

(Mohammady et al., 2018) propose a solution for anonymizing network trace data prior to third party analysis, resolving an information disclosure vulnerability in the original CPAN prefix preserving solution (Xu, J. et al., 2001) by generating multiple datasets of which only the data owner can reidentify the original, not considered for the project due to complexity

More recent synthesis of deidentification concepts and cyber event data can be found in academic contributions using pseudonymization techniques (Varanda et al., 2021; Zimmer et al., 2020) that include consistently applying pseudonyms across different data sets, a requirement for correlation analysis. (Varanda et al., 2021) demonstrated the use of custom functions within a log processing pipeline to deidentify data inline, part of the approach taken by this project. (Zimmer et al., 2020) created a framework called PEEPLL to further address potential reidentification attacks using random pseudonym generation while enabling data sharing between different parties. Both pseudonymization solutions alter sensitive field data formats, limiting use with other platforms.

In addition to maintaining global consistency to support investigation, an additional pseudonymization requirement is often retrieving original data values once a problem has been identified (GDPR, 2018c; Rasic, 2020; Varanda et al., 2021), necessitating long term storage of pseudonym mapping in both solutions above. (Chadwick et al., 2020) point out the limited value of third-party analysis of pseudonym data if the true intrusion source cannot be reidentified for response measures. Qardaji & Li, (2012) proposed applying new IP prefix-preserving pseudonyms at periodic intervals, acknowledging that the prefixes must remain consistent within the analysis period. The bucketing algorithm proposed by Qardaji & Li would not support analysis of events occurring over longer time periods since IP information would differ for each flow group.

Data Source Challenges

A Security Event Log Deidentification (SELD) project success requires replacing sensitive portions of cybersecurity event log records with data providing equivalent detection or analysis capability without confidentiality impacts. Three technical challenges that must be overcome to meet these requirements are:

- Consistent pseudonym application for all log types to facilitate correlation,
- Pseudonymized data resistance to unauthorized reidentification once shared,
- Deidentified fields values must retain original formats to enable ingestion into analysis platforms.

Pseudonymized log fields require each log entry with a specific field value like an IP address or host name be replaced with the same pseudonym to avoid distorting the dataset. Early research primarily focused on network traces (Pang et al., 2006; Xu, J. et al., 2001), but cyber event log collection now includes additional sources like application servers, authentication services and operating systems further complicating global pseudonym consistency. A precise field element like a username must be replaced with the same pseudonym to correlate event sequences across different log types. Varanda et al., (2021) proposed inline processing but transforms field data structure. Only one other inline processing solution, applying transformation functions based on field data type during data ingest was identified in the literature. A modular approach for processing multiple log types, FLAIM, an NCSA research project (Slagell et al., 2006), appears long retired but provided conceptual validation for the SELD approach.

Once deidentified, SELD requires cyber event logs to retain their original format to allow ingesting into an existing security investigation platform and identify intrusion events within that data despite both direct and indirect identifiers being modified. Deidentification solutions that replace sensitive fields with hashed or encrypted values (Menges et al., 2021; Varanda et al., 2021) limit analysis to a solution specific platform. Data must also appear realistic for effective anomaly detection whether viewed within an analyst investigation tool like a SIEM or in artificial intelligence experiment. (Teoh et al., 2018) used professional security analyst reviews of complete log data to label an AI training set. Recent cyber workforce development research advocates modular approaches to match the training exercises with the environment to be protected and realistic event data, both benign and attack (Somarakis et al., 2020; Urias et al., 2017).

Time stamp values are another pseudonymization opportunity and a constraint to be observed. Deidentified or not, cybersecurity event logs must maintain the relative time-based relationships between events and specific values within each record for context needed to differentiate benign records from intrusion indicators (Dwyer & Truta, 2013; Ho et al., 2021; Khan, S. & Parkinson, 2019; Roes, 2017). Timestamp data becomes a sensitive quasi-identifier because external sources such like news, breach reports or visual reconnaissance could provide reidentification linkage or behavioural profiling opportunities (Douriez et al., 2016; Mansour et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Hoyos et al., 2019; Tudor et al., 2015). An acknowledged gap in the current SELD solution, time stamp deidentification would require much more experimentation and validation than the project time frame permitted.

Managing Privacy and Utility Trade-offs

Cybersecurity event logs commonly take the form of attribute tuples, have predefined structure and data formats, and may contain sensitive data regarding system's security posture (Khan, S. & Parkinson, 2019). Modern log volume often exceeds millions, and occasionally billions of events per day (IBM, 2021; Microsoft, 2022b). This rich data mining environment facilitates

system resilience and cybersecurity assurance enabling security professionals to combine their domain expertise with big data techniques (DeYoung, 2018). Unfortunately, larger collections of semi-structured data accessed through analytic engines add reidentification risk due to the volume of indirect identifiers and unique patterns created within this (DeYoung, 2018; Montjoye, De et al., 2013; Narayanan & Felten, E., 2019) data. The “honest but curious” (HBC) external data-handler is an adversarial consideration in privacy related research papers, including maintaining organizational privacy with an outsourced managed security service provider (MSSP) (Rasic, 2020; Zhang et al., 2006). How data can be reanalyzed or combined with other sources in the future to derive new insights is unknowable to the organization sharing the deidentified data (Douriez et al., 2016; Garfinkel, S. L., 2015; Narayanan et al., 2016; Sweeney, 1997) therefore risk assessment should precede data sharing.

Traditional prevention measures like high degrees of generalization and aggregation or removing individual data identifiers to create statistical analysis datasets with reduced privacy concern (Golle, 2006) are ineffective approaches for sharing investigable cybersecurity event data. (Chadwick et al., 2020) move the cybersecurity event record privacy conversation toward a continuum decision based on the detail level needed by the data processors and their stakeholders. Acceptable privacy levels are achieved through data sharing agreements and software controls, but the authors acknowledge the solution’s complexity and inability to share between different trust levels. Ohm (2010) summarized this tension a decade earlier as

"Utility and privacy are, at bottom, two goals at war with one another. In order to be useful, anonymized data must be imperfectly anonymous".

The seminal work “Broken Promises of Privacy” (Ohm, 2010) analyses data anonymization issues from a legal policy perspective, often referencing the earlier, highly influential “Weaving Technology and Policy Together to Maintain Confidentiality” (Sweeney, 1997). NIST IR 8053 (Garfinkel, S. L., 2015) revisits both papers and several other sources further defining deidentification techniques from a procedural practice perspective. Although Garfinkel and Ohm cite the AOL 2006 reidentification report (Barbaro & Zeller, 2006) their protection focus is PII rather than attributing cyber events to a specific person, which until recently was not considered PII(Hintze, 2018).

Garfinkel (2015), points out the European privacy committee Article 29 Working Party do not consider pseudonymized data anonymized but do consider it a security control (Emam, El & Alvarez, 2015), a similar position later reflected in GDPR article 32 (GDPR, 2018c). Consequently, organizations contemplating cyber event data sharing, are left with the burden of assessing reidentification risk themselves and knowingly or not, already participate. Technical support issues with IT systems often require sharing sensitive system data and many organizations employ third party data analysis for some cybersecurity services (Gartner, 2022), deidentification is not the norm in either scenario.

Organizations in specific industries may also be participating in government managed/mandated threat monitoring (Canarie, 2021; TSA, 2022) or Information Sharing and Analysis Centers (ISAC). (Chadwick et al., 2020) identify the need for data sharing agreements and differing degrees of deidentification within their framework but for the security leader ultimately accountable for the likelihood and impact of reidentification risks the research is not straightforward. ISO 31000 defines risk as the “effect of uncertainty on objectives”(Tranchard,

2018) and list IT, organizational resilience, crisis management and security among the many risk receptors that management systems must address, therefore contributing to cyber security research may be the best long-term solution.

Policy maker interest in quasi-identifiers leading to the reidentification of individuals seems to coincide with research literature on digital-to-physical reidentification using pseudonymized smart meter and mobile location data (Cleemput et al., 2018; Finster & Baumgart, 2013; Montjoye, De et al., 2013). Despite proving reidentification feasibility, researchers did not report legal or physical consequences, though potentially a future impact as quasi-identifiers gain consideration in privacy regulations.

There is also debate on the practicality of reidentification attacks, proponents draw attention to external data requirements and very low success rates when the deidentified datasets are analyzed within designated boundaries (Cavoukian & Castro, 2014) and the accuracy of identification claims (Barbaro & Zeller, 2006). Opponents point out the fallacy of predicting all data sources, current and future, an attacker could have access to perform reidentification attacks (Narayanan & Felten, E., 2019; Narayanan et al., 2016). Although Narayanan et al dismiss ad hoc deidentification as inadequate privacy protection, pseudonymization within security products is not widely commercially available today. Assessing GDPR compliant data processing viability with an experimental SEIM, (Menges et al., 2021) acknowledge future work needed to address certain incident identification gaps their research uncovered.

Organizations have controls beyond deidentification such as limiting the volume of data shared, vetted recipients versus public release (Narayanan et al., 2016) and periodic pseudonym rotation (Qardaji & Li, 2012). Additionally, reidentification within cybersecurity event logs will typically be limited to quasi-identifiers like IP addresses, event time or computer account names, data like passwords are typically not logged. Research has long shown service and system identification is possible without verbatim reidentification (Coull et al., 2007; Khan, S. & Parkinson, 2019; Murakami, 2019). While identification of topology or vulnerable hosts is less than ideal, the adversary must gain access to the environment then bypass other security controls before gaining full access (Kordy et al., 2014). When control measures, potential impacts and benefits are considered, certain cyber event log sharing scenarios may be within an organization's risk tolerance allowing consideration of this projects deidentification program.

Project Software Solution Requirements

Digital events now occur in almost all aspects of daily life, and many generate a record of that event occurring. A person commuting to work makes an electronic payment for transit and at some future point in time the exact amount transfers from their bank account to the transit operator. Upon arrival, the commuter may hold an RFID badge next to a reader to gain access to their office and then be prompted for their username and password while logging into a computer. Each electronic interaction has the potential to be recorded for further use or analysis, but decisions regarding what to collect and how to process that information are primarily dependent on the system owners and operators. The transit operator and bank most certainly took actions based on the purchase while the RFID event may have been retained only long enough to validate access and unlock the door.

Specific to this thesis, the computer recorded the login event, and it is presumed the organization collected it for monitoring. This project’s scope is limited to network, computer and application events normally equated with the term “cybersecurity” but even a cursory review of cyber event logging guidance affirms there are many factors for consideration(Kent & Souppaya, 2006). The following framework is proposed for gathering requirements and identifying processes needed for creating realistic cyber event data in a deidentified form in a programmatic way.

Figure 3.1 SELD Conceptual Framework

Figure 3.1 summarizes the cyber event log deidentification process into four core phases needed for a comprehensive solution. Anticipating different organizational needs, the intention was modular phases would have general requirements, inputs and outputs but flexibility within each module could enable expansion and additional research.

Cyber Event Data Source Selection

Although centralized log record collection via network stream is common, alternative collection approaches include periodic querying of database tables or APIs storing audit events, a scheduled import of CSV formatted output from of a nightly mainframe batch or any other record regularly generated by an electronic system (Chuvakin et al., 2013). Ideally, the cyber event log sources selected for monitoring would align to the most impactful organizational threats, not collection solely for compliance. Consequence based modeling has proven valuable for identifying cyber threats significant impact, and by extension, required monitoring sources but tends to be a lengthy process (Bochman & Freeman, 2021). Consequently, organizations often align with monitoring requirements specified by regulation (European Commission, 2010; PCI SSC, 2022) or follow preliminary threat use cases recommended by industry experts (Bejtlich, 2013; Murdoch, 2018). That said, the project's modular approach to deidentification should be useable or extendable for any cyber event log source since individual log record entries are merely a concatenated set of fields.

This proof-of-concept demonstrates a deidentification approach rather than a complete system for cyber intrusion monitoring, therefore, the following three distinct log source categories have been select to develop and validate the initial software solution:

- Linux auth or authpriv logs
- Windows Security event logs and PowerShell Operational Logs
- Stateful Firewall logs (BSD based PFSense)

The rationale for the Windows and Linux operating systems was their prevalence in government and private industry. These sources also collect account and network perimeter activity, common requirements in most cyber monitoring regulation. Although industry specific context would still be required for effective training, the deidentification process is based on record structure which remains constant within a given operating system version, regardless of the organization using the computer. The presumption is that an organization collecting additional events not included in the proof-of-concept set could extend the software modules to extract and deidentify other sensitive fields by following the guidance provided in Appendix B.

The PFSense firewall, like almost all modern firewall platforms, can export records of blocked and permitted traffic using the RFC 3164 or RFC 5424 Syslog messaging format. Firewall rule logs invariably include observed IP addresses, protocols and service ports as well as the rule outcome and often include additional context depending on firewall features. Appendix B details the transformation process but in many cases the mechanism developed for deidentification of stateful firewall data should only require parser template modifications to work with other firewall brands not process re-engineering.

Data Requirements Identification

Balancing privacy with utility is a recurring theme within the literature, policy makers, GDPR, NIST and the Ontario Privacy commission defining deidentification criteria without defining utility levels was not unexpected. Conversely, some researchers took optimistic views toward utility (DeYoung, 2018; Menges et al., 2021; Varanda et al., 2021), presenting deidentification solutions with limited applicability beyond research.

From a practical perspective, industry regulation pertaining to cyber event log data collection lands on the prescriptive end of the privacy-utility continuum, requiring event sources that specifically identify the actions of individuals. Although wording differs, multiple internationally recognized standards are consistent on the types of fields within a cyber event log that must be collected to support an investigation (European Commission, 2010; ISMS, 2023; Joint Task Force, 2020; PCI SSC, 2022). Therefore, project data source selections aligning to these standards also became a commitment to deidentify specific quasi-identifiers like account names and IP addresses. Table 3.1 summarizes the required fields and indicates which of these fields can be quasi-identifiers leading to reidentification.

Table 3.1 Privacy considerations by data field types

Field Context	Details or Examples	Sensitive quasi-identifier
Event Type	Login, account change, firewall block, service stop	Potentially*
Event time	Time and date reported by OS, firewall, application	No
Event Location	Source and destination systems, IP addresses, geo-location meta data,	Yes
Event Source	Program or process responsible for event	Potentially**
Event Outcome	Success or failure status of the action	No
Entity identity	Account names, system host names, file location names	Yes

Notes:

* Only events that include an account or group name that could be associated with an individual person, EG. The command “usermod jbeck” could potentially reidentify, “usermod root” would not.

** If the process name includes meta-data traceable to a user or organization, EG. “loginshell-jbeck” could potentially reidentify, “bash” would not.

Identifying sensitive fields is more straightforward than determining which cyber event logs will most benefit investigation. The previous framework phase identifies the need for cyber event data source selection based on regulatory compliance or threat concerns while the data requirements section must assess the technical aspects of collection. Regulations such as the EC Standard on logging and monitoring or PCI DSS define outcomes in general terms such as “User account creation, modification or deletion” (EC, 2010) while lacking specifics on how goals may be achieved. Similarly, NIST special publication 800-92 provides foundational

guidelines but developing a comprehensive cyber event log monitoring program for an organization warrants entire texts (Chuvakin et al., 2013; Virgilio & Oben, 2022).

“Under different sets of circumstances, many logs created within an organization could have some relevance to computer security...Organizations should consider the value of each potential source of computer security log data when designing and implementing a log management infrastructure.” (NIST, 2006)

Consider the NIST guidance above within the compliance context of monitoring for successful and failed authentication attempts, often addressed by organizations by collecting and counting Windows security event IDs 4624 and 4625. Unfortunately, limiting collection to these two events misses many of the events generated by Kerberos based attacks, one path toward credential compromise (Motero et al, 2021; Splunk, 2022), requiring the collection of several additional Windows security event IDs. The data requirements identification phase must also balance the anticipated needs of the cybersecurity investigator with the level of deidentification work required as each new cyber event record type can potentially have sensitive information in a different location or referenced as a different field name.

NIST 800-53 audit content record guidance does caution organizations to consider reidentification risks and specifically mentions time of usage (NIST, 2020). A design decision was made to leave the timestamps unaltered in this project phase because other quasi-identifiers are deidentified programmatically and the accurate maintenance of temporal relationships between events is a key solution benefit. Future work should explore timestamp deidentification for more public data releases since these field values may be influenceable in internet facing event sources.

Extraction Transformation and Load

By default, the Windows and Linux operating systems record both security and operational events to locally stored logfiles, suitable for a standalone machine but impractical for monitoring hundreds, or thousands of computers within an organization. Network transport of local logfile records, supporting centralized collection from multiple hosts in near real time, was included in the original BSD syslog RFC 3164 (Lonvick, 2001) and Microsoft added this capability to Windows server 2008. The Microsoft built-in solution continues to require the centralized collector to be a Windows server (Microsoft, 2023), limiting interoperability with other platforms, consequently third-party software agents that monitor and forward Windows Event Logs are included in centralized cyber event monitoring solutions (Elastic, 2023e; IBM, 2021; NXLog, n.d.).

The project lab environment will use the common centralized collection model to accept cyber event records from all host systems in the lab environment. Systems supporting either RFC3164 or RFC5424 such as Linux servers and BSD firewalls will be configured to use syslog as the transport mechanism. Windows operating systems will run Elastic’s WinLogBeat agent with the installation modified to retain Microsoft’s proprietary XML based field structure to simplify the deidentification transformation process.

Transforming field data

Multiple technical approaches network-based record collection exist, challenges immediately appear when individual fields within those records need to be identified and field values extracted for deidentification processing. Simply put, extraction becomes complicated because there is no well adopted standard for field names, field location within the record or data structures of critical values like timestamps (Chuvakin et al., 2013; Kent & Souppaya, 2006). The previous section discussed preliminary data selection and collection steps which can be unique to an organization and likely require industry specific cybersecurity expertise for optimum value. Two subsequent processes within the activity pipeline, extracting and transforming data from a cyber event record are industry agnostic data processing allowing for future enhancement and optimization using skilled programmers. Within this project phase, cyber event data sources will be limited to records initially stored in log files, excluding event record formats often required for data breach forensic investigations and advanced troubleshooting such as binary images of memory processes or hard-disks and network packet captures. Table 3.2 summarizes the advantages and challenges of the three log file categories likely to be regularly observed within organizations.

Table 3.2 Log record parsing requirements by type

Original Source Format	Extraction Process	Benefits	Drawbacks
Binary stream	Split data on known byte boundaries, store in predefined locations	Lowest processing time, highest record precision, potentially smallest record size	New extraction process for each source or variation, not human readable
Key-value structure	Field names define storage taxonomy, split data on predefined delimiter(s)	Field value size and data type flexibility,	Field name schema is arbitrary, increased record size due key-value and delimiter
Freeform text	Select field values using text parsing, (regular expressions, string slicing etc.)	Human readable, no key-value overhead, extremely flexible parsing	Slowest processing time, parsing requires significant domain knowledge and is error prone

Key-value and freeform text cyber event record structures will be used to develop and validate the deidentification process created using the following requirements:

- Deidentification processes will use pseudonymization to provide privacy protection for sensitive field values selected during the framework's data requirements identification phase,

- The pseudonymization process must be implemented via software modules that are independent of the field value extraction method,
- Pseudonymization modules must accept sensitive field value inputs returning deidentified outputs of the same data format,
- The pseudonymization algorithms must utilize a set of cipher key values generated by, and known only to the original data owner (ODO) or original data processor (ODP),
- Deidentified cyber event records should be sufficiently indistinguishable from original counterparts in visual form and structure ensuring common cyber analyst actions can be performed within analytics platform,
- Syslog formatted records transformed through the deidentification process must retain the same format to enable direct ingestion and parsing into analytics platforms supporting that data source in syslog format,
- Proprietary formats such as Windows Event log must be output as JSON lines post deidentification while retaining the original field names and timestamp format, acknowledging additional reformatting is likely required for analytics platform ingestion.

Converting records not already in RFC3164 or RFC5424 syslog format into JSON lines may initially appear to conflict with the format preservation requirements stated by the project. The JSON lines format should be viewed as an intermediary storage mechanism enabling deidentified data sharing. Well-structured file-based datasets are often easiest to work with and it is assumed that a qualified 3DP will be capable of creating or modifying a data ingestion program to populate their analytics platform without ODO or ODP assistance beyond a manifest defining less obvious fieldnames in JSON lines formatted record sets. This 3DP capability requirement can be used as both vetting criteria and facilitate the use of an intermediary or escrow when higher source anonymity is required.

To demonstrate the viability of this approach, additional software programs must be created to read in the structured data sets and load the data into an analytics platform. The project has made extensive use of the Elastic product suite, often referred to as “the ELK stack” which includes “Elasticsearch”, a document storage database, and “Kibana” an intuitive, web browser-based searching tool. For validation purposes, Elasticsearch and Kibana will be considered the cyber event analytics program and the custom input process to load the data from file will use the Logstash processing engine with a custom configuration transforming original field names into the elastic common schema (Elastic, 2022a).

Investigation Suitability Validation

The reasoning behind field deidentification has been addressed in the literature review and specifics regarding various fields are addressed in later sections of this report. One testable success criterion for the deidentified data deliverables is the ability to import a log file containing deidentified cyber event records into a log analysis platform using a programmatic ingestion option available to that platform. An additional testable success criterion is analyst search activities within deidentified data should remain the same with the understanding that certain fields may have slight visual differences due to character replacement in the encryption process required for certain sensitive fields.

To validate investigation suitability both benign and malicious cyber events will be staged within the lab environment. Unit test definitions, rationale and results have been included in the evaluation section with the caveat that the project goal is to validate the deidentification process, providing an input data for cyber intrusion detection development, not intrusion detection research itself. Like the first two framework phases, industry specific cybersecurity experience may provide valuable guidance in this framework phase on two fronts. First validating relevant observables are properly represented in the deidentified dataset; and second, confirmation sensitive data enabling reidentification does not appear in the data.

The following testing activities must be performed within the ELK analytics platform to confirm multiple deidentification requirements have been met:

- A predefined search that would be performed by an analyst, executed on both the original and deidentified data will the same number of events in the same time sequence, (within precision limitations of the platform and originating sources).
- A search for IP addresses, computer, domain, or account names designated as sensitive will return no results in the deidentified set.
- A search for the deidentified value of an IP or account name should return the same record count in the deidentified data as the search for the original
- Within the deidentified records event format and details must remain the same as illustrated in the following example:

Original: "2023-02-12 14:23:06 user **bsmith** failed authentication from **10.11.12.22**"

Deident: "2023-02-12 14:23:06 user **uisd1o** failed authentication from **10.87.14.26**"

- The deidentified data within a record can be quickly reidentified by anyone with access to the key set used for pseudonymization, possibly through a rest API call or standalone script.

Research Design and Solution Implementation

The SELD project had short timelines and software development requirements, therefore an agile delivery approach was adopted for the data processing components. Figure 4.1 illustrates a great deal of iteration was anticipated developing the software modules transforming the cyber event log data generated in the lab environment into deidentified records. This assumption proved correct for reasons outlined later in this section. While the software modules and processing pipeline are required to demonstrate process viability, the research hypothesis focus is confirmation that data source privacy is maintained while providing sufficient elements within each record to enable cyber security investigations within the deidentified event data.

Figure 4.1 SELD project milestones

Cyber Event Data Source Selection - Implementation

Defining log source requirements for an organization is beyond this project's scope and directly addressed in several regulatory frameworks (European Commission, 2010; Joint Task Force, 2020; PCI SSC, 2022). Additionally, widely deployed cyber technology generating event records used for observability and security investigations number in the hundreds (IBM, 2023; Splunk, 2023) and easily exceed thousands when custom applications are included for consideration (Chuvakin et al., 2013; Majors et al., 2022). Since analyzing each log source was infeasible, Linux authlog, Windows Event Log and PFSense firewall log records were used throughout the project, based on the requirements defined in chapter 3.

Data Requirements Identification – Implementation

Table 3.1 summarized the fields all identified regulatory bodies considered mandatory for collection and which of these fields will need to be deidentified. To maintain deidentified data utility the project decision was to apply pseudonymization techniques to IP addresses and sensitive text data, creating a critical dependence on field extraction accuracy.

By default, the Linux operating system uses the syslog program as an event logging facility. Linux kernel and application software developers define which events are captured and utilize the syslog facility definitions for categorization. Fortunately, by long standing convention, Linux events pertaining to authentication or authorization are written to the auth facility allowing a single file to be monitored for all account related events(Garfinkel, S. & Spafford, 1996; Singer, A. & Bird, 2004), a common logging regulation requirement(European Commission, 2010; ISMS, 2023; PCI SSC, 2022).

Although directing all Linux authentication events to a single file simplifies collection, identifying specific conditions within the freeform text content requires extensive parsing. Elastic's Logstash software includes an optimized regular expression engine to process individual event records upon input but nuanced variations in log messages can lead to field value extraction errors (Golubenco, 2017). An overview on how the project managed this complexity appears in chapter four and technical details in Appendix B.

Conversely, the Windows Event Log specification requires identification numbers for each event type collected by logging channels, (a channel is like a "facility" in the syslog specification), creating an efficient preliminary filtering option to focus supplementary processing on specific deidentification tasks. Event ID and channel were also used as filtering criteria to drop high noise, low value events and assign metadata tagging to efficiently direct deidentification processing.

Reidentification Protection

Legal statutes referring to deidentification of personal data acknowledge technical limitations, requiring data owners and processors to reasonably foresee or anticipate how the data could be used to reidentify an individual (GDPR, 2018b; Sookman, 2022). GDPR articles 25 and 32 include pseudonymization as protection measure calling for technical and procedural measures to ensure security measures are risk appropriate, stopping short of defining a determination approach. Consequently, the following technical control requirements have been identified for implementation within the SELD software and recommended workflow.

- Records failing to match a predefined pattern during the extraction process must be written to separate log for additional analysis,
- Prior to release deidentified data should be searched known sensitive keywords using a software tool rather than rely on human review,
- The pseudonymization key set must not be shared with third party data processors and stored securely within the organization,
- Organizations should record which datasets were shared, with whom, and the key set used for pseudonymization.

Since additional external data is typically required, reidentification viability using quasi-identifiers within deidentified data, and the subsequent impacts, is an area of research and debate (IPC Ontario, 2016; Mansour et al., 2021; Narayanan & Felten, E., 2019; Rocher et al., 2019). This project considered internal IP addresses, computer hostnames, account names and the domain names associated with the organization as sensitive since they can often be observed in aggregate to identify patterns. Appendix F documents how reidentification within the SELD platform could occur, Appendix E considers the impact of reidentification in a risk assessment and Appendix D lists the events and field data considered for as potential quasi-identifiers requiring deidentification processing of some type.

Platform Implementation

From inception the SELD project focus has been a programmatic deidentification of sensitive cyber event record fields to facilitate data sharing, but demonstrating how deidentified event data could be used by a third-party data processor would require a SIEM or log aggregation solution. The Elastic “ELK Stack” was chosen as the underlying delivery platform for the proof of concept for several reasons including:

- Significant market share, 5-billion-dollar market capitalization, strong software release and maintenance practices (Elastic, 2023c),
- Many commercial features are freely available, allowing access to researchers and educational institutions with limited budgets,
- Prebuilt reliable modules for data collection and export to more than 50 storage, monitoring, and transport technologies (Elastic, 2023d)

Figure 4.2 SELD collection & preliminary processing

Figure 4.2 conceptually illustrates the raw event collection and preliminary processing required before the SELD framework *Extraction, Transformation and Load* phase but obscures the complexity of centralized collection of multiple data sources. The discussion below illustrates how a project specific problem was able to be addressed using different elements from Elastic’s suite of software products, further validating the development platform decision. For brevity’s sake, this chapter only highlights where technical decisions intersect with key requirements or problems identified during solution implementation, Appendix A includes technical detail on the event collection pipeline.

Collection and processing at scale

Despite being one of the world's most widely deployed operating systems, centrally collecting, and analyzing event logs from networked Windows computers is somewhat complex. For performance reasons the Windows operating system generated and stores log records in a propriety binary format that requires special software to create human readable events. The built-in Windows Event Viewer, designed to read the proprietary format, is adequate when working directly on a Windows computer or reviewing a small number of exported log files but fails for centralized event monitoring.

Figure 4.3 Binary format made human readable

Some software agents developed over the years transformed the Windows binary message into syslog format to facilitate network transport to a centralized log collection service as shown in figure 4.3 (NXLog, n.d.) requiring text-based parsing which impacts ingestion performance and accuracy (Table 3.2).

```
<11>Nov 1 18:52:56 NXLOG-AGENT MSWinEventLog 3 Security 2 Thu Nov 01 18:52:56 2018 4625 Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing N/A N/A Failure Audit
NXLOG-AGENT Logon An account failed to log on. Subject: Security ID: S-1-0-0 Account Name: - Account Domain: - Logon ID: 0x0 Logon Type: 3 Account For
Which Logon Failed: Security ID: S-1-0-0 Account Name: ADMINISTRATOR Account Domain: Failure Information: Failure Reason: Unknown user name or bad
password. Status: 0xC000006D Sub Status: 0xC000006A Process Information: Caller Process ID: 0x0 Caller Process Name: - Network Information: Workstation
Name: - Source Network Address: XXXX Source Port: 0 Detailed Authentication Information: Logon Process: NtLmSsp Authentication Package: NTLM Transited
Services: - Package Name (NTLM only): - Key Length: 0
```

Figure 4.4 Windows Event RFC3164 format (NXLog, n.d.)

The Microsoft event log API translates the binary format to XML (Microsoft, 2020), creating a key-value-based event, Elastic's Winlogbeat agent (Elastic, 2023e) enables this XML formatted data to be transported over the network as JSON (Fig. 4.6).

Winlogbeat, an actively maintained software agent from Elastic, stores configuration settings in an editable YAML file, suitable for a common collection capability across as many computers as

needed. To retain Microsoft’s XML key-value structure, the Winlogbeat agent’s default configuration file must be modified with an additional YAML stanza and log source attributes updated to include the additional data as shown in figure 4.5.

```
processors:
  - decode_xml_wineventlog:
      field: event.original
      target_field: winlog

winlogbeat.event_logs:
  - name: Application
    include_xml: true
    ignore_older: 168h

  - name: System
    include_xml: true

  ...
```

Figure 4.5 YAML modifications for XML collection

Figure 4.6 shows the output of the local XML data illustrated in figure 4.2 transported over the network to a centralized collection service then further processed using Logstash codecs and plugins to create JSON lines record entries. JSON lines format separates each individual record with a newline instead of appending all records into a single document, providing the ability to access an individual record as a file line while retaining the key-value relationship. This simplifies parsing and allows for parallel processing of large files since each record becomes atomic in the JSON lines format.

```
dleece@infsec19:/var/tmp$ grep 1314595 winevts.jsonl-2023-03-16
{"computer_name":"infsvc09.ymmv.local","process":{"pid":604,"thread":{"id":1476},"keywords":["Audit Success"],"level":"information","channel":"Security","event_data":{"LogonType":"3","TargetLogonId":"0x1b25fd4","TargetUserName":"INFVC09$","TargetDomainName":"YMMV","TargetUserSid":"S-1-5-18"},"message":"An account was logged off.\n\nSubject:\n\nSecurity ID:\t\tS-1-5-18\n\nAccount Name:\t\tINFVC09$\n\nAccount Domain:\t\tYMMV\n\nLogon ID:\t\t0x1B25FD4\n\nLogon Type:\t\t3\n\nThis event is generated when a logon session is destroyed. It may be positively correlated with a logon event using the Logon ID value. Logon IDs are only unique between reboots on the same computer."},"opcode":"Info","record_id":1314595,"event_id":4634,"task":"Logoff","provider_guid":{"54849625-5478-4994-A5BA-3E3B0328C30D"},"time_created":"2023-03-16T00:00:36.731Z","provider_name":"Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing","outcome":"success"}
```

Figure 4.6 XML message converted to JSON lines

IP Address Pseudonymization

At its core, pseudonymization simply means replacing sensitive data within a record with similar mock data (Garfinkel, 2015). For example, changing “*Bob Waters, 829 easy street, Chicago*” to “*Fred Flintstone, 123 Granite Lane, Bedrock*” maintains the data structure and protects privacy but pseudonymization becomes more complicated when dealing with cyber event logs for three reasons:

- Data record elements such as an IP address cannot be random, the pseudonym address must be changed to a similar network range as the neighbouring IP addresses also requiring changing, while remaining unique within the subnet containing all the pseudonymized hosts (Pang et al, 2006).
- A pseudonymized element must be changed in all other records in which the element appears because cyber investigations often rely on following a series of actions within different log source vantage points to discern malicious activity (Amaro et al., 2022; Lee, R., 2012).

- Log aggregation and analysis platform database schemas often require specific data types and formats for indexing, and human analysts must be able to recognize the data format to make certain determinations quickly(Cherniashchuk & Kostiucho, 2022).

Table 4.1 illustrates flow-tuple-based examples commonly collected from network firewall or intrusion detection systems and two deidentification approaches.

Table 4.1 Network Flow Records

Flow Tuple ID	Source address	Source port	Destination IP	Dest'n Port
Original network flow tuples				
A	10.21.39.39	1412	10.21.30.10	445
B	10.21.39.39	1337	52.108.248.37	443
C	10.21.39.39	14161	10.21.39.56	3389
Hash based pseudonyms				
A.1	3d9de5a1b2c50e66f88e4 324cbe05c9a5bece631	623	0a4133feeaf5c6e7d8f4383f d561d0dafdc3f80e	445
B.1	3d9de5a1b2c50e66f88e4 324cbe05c9a5bece631	87234	52.108.248.37	443
C.1	3d9de5a1b2c50e66f88e4 324cbe05c9a5bece631	12746	87fd40d562ba2154cfca877 db0a8929051bf551b	3389
Rotational cipher pseudonyms				
A.2	10.87.12.14	1516	10.87.3.240	445
B.2	10.87.12.14	1412	52.108.248.37	443
C.2	10.87.12.14	15212	10.87.12.31	3389

Analysts familiar with network communication patterns and parameters would likely conclude from examples A and B that a single host connected to an internal server in another network within the organization and an external hosted website or cloud service using the HTTPS protocol. Flow examples A.1-C.1 illustrate replacing IP addresses with hashed data values, (Varanda et al., 2021) , accomplishing the privacy goal but the hash values in the destination IP column prevent an analyst differentiating the traffic between internal hosts, potentially problematic when communication tuple C.1 is evaluated. Flow examples A.2-C.2 show the source address 10.21.39.39 has been changed while maintaining the mathematical relationship to the neighbouring host in the same subnet.

SELD Rotational cipher

The bytes used to define IP addresses can be treated as rotors, adding, or subtracting a common value to maintain the networking relationship between neighbouring hosts. RFC1918 range IP addresses, extracted from cyber event records, are pseudonymized using a rotational substitution algorithm with different rotational values assigned to segments being shifted, like polyalphabetic ciphers such as Vigenère. Figure 4.7 illustrates how IP addresses are divided into a static prefix and two shiftable segments assigned new values derived from a set of numbers generated and retained by the data owner or delegated processor.

Figure 4.7 SELD pseudonymization algorithm

To obfuscate each IP more effectively, different mathematical operations are used to calculate the shift offset distance and direction for each shiftable segment. A code section from the IP cipher module, (Fig 4.8), highlights the use of different key set elements (*tk*s) for shift calculations. Since the original IP address value is used in each calculation, and the resulting intermediary large number is reduced using modulo arithmetic, the inside segment value shifts by differing amounts than the right most host segment, confounding reidentification because multiple numbers, known only to the original data owner, contribute to shift values.

```

# RFC 1918 / 12
if dqarray[0].to_i == 172
  #Get the numeric value of the dotted quad
  ipintval = ip4obj.to_i
  # Min and max for 172.16.0.0/12
  imin=2886729728
  imax=288778273
  # flip variable to change whether an octet is added or subtracted ( further obfuscation option)
  if tks[3]
    # rotor 2 value 257 to 1033 * 256( all bits in fourth octet ),
    # Multiple by the seed to increase distance from original IP, aslo add in site random for more entropy
    of2=((tks[1] * 256) * tks[2]) + tks[4]
    deidentintval = setrotor2(ipintval,of2,imin,imax)
    #Adjust the value for the 4th octet ( rotor 1)
    rotor1 = (dqarray[3].to_i + ((tks[0] * 3) - (tks[4]/tks[2])) ) % 254
    # Add outside rotor to deidentified partial second, full third octet + prefix
    deidentintval = deidentintval + rotor1
  else
    # send offset negative
    of2=(((tks[1] * 256) * tks[2]) * -1) + tks[4]
    deidentintval = setrotor2(ipintval,of2,imin,imax)
    #Adjust the value for the 4th octet ( rotor 1)
    rotor1 = (dqarray[3].to_i - ((tks[0] * 3) + (tks[4]/tks[2])) ) % 254
    # Add second to external
    deidentintval = deidentintval + rotor1
  end
end
end

```

Figure 4.8 SELD shift calculations using key set

The Enigma machine used mechanical rotors to enable new encryption daily, and reliable decryption only when the exact rotor sequence was known (Copeland, 2023; Furness, 2021). The mathematics within the SELD module does not claim Enigma level robustness although the more dynamic middle offset prevents a key that coincidentally decrypts one network address from correctly decrypting hosts from a different subnet.

Text Data Pseudonymization

Unlike IP addresses, text-based data uses far less than 255 characters and dictionaries of valid language patterns are plentiful, therefore more robust encryption was for data values like computer hostnames, domain names and accounts. Within data such as a domain name, the text characters required encryption but delimiters like “.” needed to remain cleartext for correct format and searchability within an analysis platform. Table 4.2 illustrates how a common cyber attributes like email address and Windows Active Directory user principle names (UPN) would appear following various encryption approaches.

Table 4.2 Encryption Output samples

	Latonia.Mathews@Widgets.Org	rsingh@widgets.org
Encryption model		
Rotational cipher: Single shift	Wlezytl.Xlesphd@Htorped.Zcr	cdtyrs@htorped.zcr
SHA1 hash	fb5548bb1394cfeae09ebe4b4d4fd9001bcaba78	d744f25885a55921491f6e41802954f2d757ab62
AES 128 bit	IVbTJit/u6/ZGfVo9j7/XQBm3qNs3W+OdMaGMb65FYM=	XvNoYjkY0nJd6oWwH0zE6Y3L0yygjb28np2Wi+id54=
FPE complete	JVMbvRh.@AuMlwgrqIBcDLNFTW	KGKbcYwRAZoP.JLSDG
FPE delimiter aware	rHnFYGzwnVwDPpu@ eGHGmiT,vmB	QvKsQT@vyMdkEv,acn

The rotational cipher approach meets the utility requirement, and the encrypted records are syntactically like original sources. Unfortunately, the domain name structure makes simple rotational ciphers particularly weak, testing with a handful of three letter top level domains like “.net”, “.com”, “.biz”, immediately contributes three letters to the puzzle. Applying the same rotational cipher values to the domain name itself reduces identification to seconds due to many public lists an adversary could use to validate shift tests against.

Directly opposite to shift ciphers, SHA1 and AES 128-bit processing are highly resistance to reidentification but do not syntactically resemble the original sources. Consequently, searching within an analytics platform or aggregating by portions of the domain name fail with both hashing and symmetric key encryption of the complete field value.

As the name implies, format preserving encryption (FPE) retains the number and type of characters used in the original but transforms the data based on symmetric key inputs.

Originally designed for financial and government applications to encrypt credit card and social insurance numbers, NIST adopted the FF1 and FF3 implementations in 2016 but flaws discovered by multiple cryptographic researchers (Durak & Vaudenay, 2017; Hoang et al., 2018), led to an updated specification in 2019 to ensure 128-bit encryption is applied in all cases (Dworkin, 2019). The updated specification was implemented in a popular Python module called FF3 (Schoening, 2019), which was used for SELD.

SELD Format Preserving Encryption Implementation

The Logstash engine includes many built-in processing modules, called plugins, and supports data directed to custom scripts written in the Ruby programming language (Duarte, 2018). During the project not public Ruby gem implementing FF3-1 was identified, consequently a REST API using Python FF3 was developed for applying FPE to text-based values extracted from cyber event records processed by the Logstash pipeline. Figure 4.9 shows the data values will be padded with “_” characters if the minimum data length for encryption is not met. A key generation program was also created for the project to reduce the chance of introducing the null byte vulnerability identified by FF3 researchers.

```
# Retrieve the FPE key values and instantiate the cipher object
thisklist=readkeys(kpath)
key=thisklist[0]
tweak=thisklist[1]
fpename = FF3Cipher.withCustomAlphabet(key,tweak,compnamealpha)

# Create a second encryption object for encrypting numbers only, EG Windows SID
fpenumonly = FF3Cipher(key,tweak)

# FPE has minimum lengths, 4 chars for alpha, 6 chars for radix10 ( digits)
def testelemalpha(thiselem):
    if len(thiselem) < 4:
        thiselem = thiselem.rjust(4,"_")
    return thiselem

def testelemdigit(thiselem):
    if len(thiselem) < 6:
        thiselem = thiselem.rjust(6,"0")
    return thiselem
```

Figure 4.9 Enforcing domain size FF3-1

Field Data Extraction

Randomly selected cyber event records from three distinct sources, (Fig 4.10), illustrate the sources differ enough to warrant separate Logstash pipelines using individual configuration files to simplify code management. Figure 4.11 presents a different challenge, all the records were collected from a single Linux server and generated by a privileged user creating a new account, considered mandatory monitoring events by most regulatory standards (European Commission, 2010; ISMS, 2023; PCI SSC, 2022).

```

<85>Mar 19 22:40:35 invsvc59 unix_chkpwd[14876]: password check failed for user (root)

<134>1 2023-03-19T19:13:20.220788-06:00 infsec04.ymmv.local filterlog 14039 - - 102,,1665852414,em2,match,pass,in,4,0x0,,64,10792,0,none,17,udp,90,192.168.40.57,64.4.48.3,59291,53,70

{"computer_name":"infsvc09.ymmv.local","process":{"pid":604,"thread":{"id":3280},"keywords":["Audit Success"],"level":"information","channel":"Security","event_data":{"ProcessName":"-","LogonGuid":{"13FBFB34-5D4F-B5B3-C5ED-F8BCDD94FA45"},"TargetOutboundDomainName":"-","VirtualAccount":{"%1843"},"IpPort":{"56399"},"TransmittedServices":"-","LmPackageName":"-","RestrictedAdminMode":"-","ElevatedToken":{"%1842"},"WorkstationName":"-","SubjectDomainName":"-","TargetDomainName":"YMMV.LOCAL","LogonProcessName":"Kerberos","LogonType":"3","SubjectLogonId":"0x0","TargetOutboundUserName":"-","KeyLength":"0","TargetLogonId":"0x2661173","SubjectUserName":"-","TargetLinkedLogonId":"0x0","IpAddress":{"::1"},"ImpersonationLevel":{"%1833"},"TargetUserName":"INFSVC09$","ProcessId":"0x0","SubjectUserSid":"S-1-0-0","AuthenticationPackageName":"Kerberos","TargetUserSid":"S-1-5-18"},"opcode":"Info","version":2,"record_id":1358528,"event_id":"4624","task":"Logon","provider_guid":{"548849625-5478-4994-A5BA-3E3B0328C30D"},"time_created":"2023-03-20T00:56:39.0302","provider_name":"Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing","outcome":"success"}

```

Figure 4.10 Log samples, three source types

```

<86>Mar 20 18:13:01 infdev22 sshd[8764]: Accepted password for dleece from 10.20.30.24 port 48434 ssh2
<85>Mar 20 18:18:34 infdev22 sudo[8824]: dleece : TTY=pts/0 ; FWD=/home/dleece ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/sbin/useradd -m -d /opt/oracle oradev
<86>Mar 20 18:18:34 infdev22 useradd[8831]: new group: name=oradev, GID=1004
<86>Mar 20 18:18:34 infdev22 useradd[8831]: new user: name=oradev, UID=1002, GID=1004, home=/opt/oracle, shell=/bin/bash, from=/dev/pts/0
<86>Mar 20 18:18:34 infdev22 sudo[8824]: pam_unix(sudo:session): session opened for user root(uid=0) by dleece(uid=1000)
<86>Mar 20 18:18:35 infdev22 sudo[8824]: pam_unix(sudo:session): session closed for user root
<86>Mar 20 18:19:07 infdev22 sudo[8842]: pam_unix(sudo:session): session opened for user root(uid=0) by dleece(uid=1000)
<85>Mar 20 18:19:07 infdev22 sudo[8842]: dleece : TTY=pts/0 ; FWD=/home/dleece ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/bin/passwd oradev
<85>Mar 20 18:19:16 infdev22 passwd[8844]: pam_unix(passwd:chauthtok): password changed for oradev
<86>Mar 20 18:19:16 infdev22 sudo[8842]: pam_unix(sudo:session): session closed for user root

```

Figure 4.11 Log variance, same source

As mentioned previously, most of the Linux syslog RFC3164 or RFC5424 record format is a freeform field which requires extensive text parsing. Both syslog RFC formats do present the event time, source computer and name of the process or program generating the event in a consistent order (Fig 4.12) while the remaining portion of the record varies significantly.

Figure 4.12 Initial syslog processing in Logstash

A design decision was made to split the Linux messages into two segments, the initial structured section and the freeform section containing the remainder of each message. The third field extracted from the initial structured section was the source process field which was used to assign metadata tagging to the event. Metadata tags were used to select a group of regular expressions to test the free form field against, limiting pattern testing to known syntax for a given type of record, I.E., do not test for SUDO specific patterns with SSH events. Positive matches resulted in additional metadata tag assignments, records with unmatched freeform data were diverted to a review log. Appendix B expands on the process above as well as background context on Logstash features used in this pipeline and examples of how the process was implemented in project code.

Additional Pipeline Processing

Figures 4.13 and 4.14 show the processing pipeline for both Linux and Windows events using files containing Linux syslog formatted records or JSON lines. Both extraction processes have been discussed earlier in this chapter, the additional post processing is directing the extracted events to the appropriate Ruby modules, performing the deidentification functions discussed previously then reassembling the events into their original input format. Appendix A includes both the important Logstash pipeline configuration elements as well as a list of Ruby modules used in the post extraction processing phases.

Figure 4.13 Conceptual model for Linux event processing

Figure 4.14 Conceptual model for Windows event processing

Evaluation

The SELD project's software development goal was a modular solution for deidentifying application and operating system event records routinely collected for cyber security monitoring without placing a significant time or resource burden on the original data owner (ODO). The purpose of deidentification would be to facilitate data sharing with vetted third-party data processors (3DP) and researchers with limited reidentification risk exposure for the ODO. From the 3DP perspective, the deidentified datasets generated by the software were also required to be suitably formatted for minimal effort importing into modern log analytics platforms, a capability demonstrated later in this chapter.

The selection of record types, security events from two operating systems and a firewall application, to demonstrate SELD approach suitability are traceable to cyber security regulations. That said, the project focus was the development of a programmatic log deidentification solution; the log sources used, and events collected (Appendix D), should be considered a representative sample rather than a recommendation of security event records to collect for optimum cyber security monitoring.

Hypothesis Validation

Table 5.1. summarizes the privacy and technical aspects of the data processing tested against the project hypothesis (chapter 1) and functional requirements (chapter 3), with supporting detail captured in this chapter's later sections or supporting appendices.

Testable Criteria	Description	Testing Outcome
IP addresses, hostname, account names and message fields are pseudonymized or encrypted	GDPR 32: Pseudonymization and encryption of personal data (GDPR Text, 2022b)	Pass
Uniquely identifiable input file metadata is removed from deidentified output	GDPR 25: Technical measures ensuring only necessary data processed (GDPR Text, 2022a)	Pass
IP addresses, hostnames and accounts cannot be linked to determine the original source organization	Article 29 Data Protection Working Party: Prevent identifying individuals by linking records within the dataset (Article 29 Working Party, 2018)	Pass
Deidentified data can be reidentified by authorized third party	GDPR 32: Timely restoration of personal data - demonstrate via rest API (GDPR Text, 2022b)	Pass

Distinct record types can be selected, filtered by search statements, and grouped by common elements	Demonstrate via third party analytics search interface	Pass
The sequence of time-based series of events is consistent between deidentified and original event source	Demonstrate via comparison within analytics platform containing both datasets	Pass
Deidentification can be implemented with minimal change to common event collection methods and analysis platforms	Documented architecture and deidentification software modules implemented in a Logstash pipeline	Pass
Deidentified data sets align to established file formats	Show output file samples aligning to JSON Lines, and Syslog formats	Pass
Deidentified data imports into publicly available analytics platform	Document import process and release Elasticsearch import configurations for Logstash	Pass

Privacy Requirements Analysis

Reidentification risk can be reduced to zero by not sharing deidentified cyber event data with any external party. This approach is not only infeasible when it comes to technical support for the many different technologies present in an organization, it also removes the opportunity for improving an organization’s cyber security posture by engaging external expertise. ISO 31000 provides risk management guidance to organizational leaders and summarizes risk as the “effect of uncertainty on objectives”(Tranchard, 2018). This statement is neither negative nor positive but an acknowledgement that senior leadership’s role in an organization is decision making.

As stated in this thesis introduction chapter, uncertainty abounds with the advancement of digitalization. Organizational leaders cannot ignore advancement, but they may also have legitimate cyber workforce concerns (ECORYS UK, 2016; Pinzone et al., 2017). Contingent collaboration with third party expertise may offer a path out of this quandary (Bresniker et al., 2019) and the use of deidentified data may provide the requisite mitigation in the event the 3DP loses control of ODO data. The organization’s senior leadership are the accountable original data owner, referred to as the “controller” in GDPR, and the use of pseudonymization is an acceptable privacy control within the regulation when the controls surrounding the process are robust (EDPB, 2020; GDPR, 2018b), therefore the decision to implement SELD and share data resides with them.

GDPR Data Pseudonymization Confirmation

The SELD software programmatically changes quasi-identifiers like account name and IP address as well as computer hostnames and process execution paths which may contain account names. Figure 5.1 illustrates a search for logon events recorded for a specific administrative user’s account, the deidentified data search (figure 5.2) is identical except for the use of deidentified pseudonym, (highlighted), as the secondary filtering criteria. Comparing the two images will also show the computer names and IP addresses have changed but retain the correct data structure and time sequence of events.

GDPR Article 32 requires deidentified data be reidentifiable by authorized entities when required, which is also a tactical need for cyber security monitoring in the event a 3DP discovers a potential intrusion. The same SELD software used to perform the pseudonym encryption can be used to decrypt the pseudonym (Fig. 5.3). The API interface to decrypt the data as well as access to encryption keys themselves would need to be highly restricted (EDPB, 2020), and additional analysis of reidentification risk has been included in Appendix E for further reflection. Finally, a complete list of potentially sensitive fields as defined by phase two of the SELD framework, and the deidentification measures taken has been included in Appendix D to assist with data regulation compliance assessment.

Figure 5.6 Administrative logon search - original data

Figure 5.7 Administrative logon search - deidentified data

Figure 5.8 Timely reidentification capability

Format Preserving Encryption

Section 4 of the Article 29 opinion on anonymization (Article 29 Working Party, 2014) states pseudonymization using state-of-the-art encryption prevents reidentification justifying the analysis of the encryption solution used in the SELD deidentification software. Format preserving encryption (FPE) use is transparent to the original data processor (ODP) since it is implemented using a REST API and the 3DP is only a reader of the deidentified data with no need for decryption. At a process level, only the ODO requires access to the encryption keys for reidentification allow tight control, a clear requirement of both the Article 29 working group and GDPR article 32, (secure processing). The alphabet used in the FPE process is 16 times the size required by NIST 800-38-gr1 for 128-bit encryption assurance (Dworkin, 2019). Additionally, both the Linux and Windows deidentification modules utilize exclusion lists to prevent encryption of well know clear text values such as “root” and “administrator” to further reduce the likelihood of successful cryptographic attacks. See Appendix B for additional details on the deidentification process.

Operational Requirements Analysis

Since the data sharing objective requires participation of organizations actively collecting cyber event data, reducing the amount of work required by the organization was a project priority. Figure 5.4 illustrates how events could be collected from multiple sources over network transport protocols and collected in a centralized location. Except for writing the output to files instead of database storage, this is essentially how most cyber security monitoring is done today (ACSC, 2021; Chuvakin et al., 2013; IBM, 2021; Kent & Souppaya, 2006.).

Figure 5.9 Conceptual example Event Record Collection

Due to the flexibility of Logstash and other collector-broker-publisher technology solutions event records could be collected one time, then, based on conditional logic within the broker node(s), directed to existing cyber security monitoring, 3DP deidentification processing or both (fig. 5.5)

Figure 5.10 Multiclient log aggregation

Although the integrated design (fig. 5.5) is potential future work, the deidentification modules provided in the initial SELD project software release do create deidentified event records conforming to either the Syslog RFC 3164, Syslog RFC 5424, or JSON Lines format. All three formats were validated via importing the data into Elasticsearch, simulating the work a 3DP would perform adding client files to their existing analytics platform. Figure 4.6 illustrates Elastic's built-in JSON codec (Elastic, 2022b) was sufficient to ingest the JSON lines file and normalization to the Elastic Common Schema (ECS) (Elastic, 2022a) was simply a matter of mapping JSON fields extracted by the codec.

```
# Convert JSON doc into field based data
filter {
  json { source => "message"
        | target => "winlog"
        | add_tag => "_json_parsed_success"
  }
}

# Modify or remove collection artifacts:
filter{

  # Remove the chance the log ingestion node contributes a hostname to the dataset that
  mutate { replace => {"[host][name]" => "3DPLoaderNode"} }
  mutate { add_field => { "[event][kind]" => "event"}}
  mutate { add_field => { "[event][outcome]" => "%{[winlog][outcome]}"}}

} # End collection artifact filter

# Correct timestamp settings:
filter {
  # Copy current timestamp to new field event.created
  mutate { add_field => { "[event][created]" => "%{@timestamp}"}}

  # move original event time in the deidentified log to the timestamp read by Kibana
  if [winlog][time_created] {
    date{
      match => ["[winlog][time_created]", "yyyy-MM-dd'T'HH:mm:ss'.SSSZ"]
      target => "@timestamp"
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 5.11 Elasticsearch import configuration code section

Each 3DP may have their own importing and normalization procedures, the project scope was limited to validating an import operation could be accomplished using features within a common log analytics platform (Nichols & Settle, 2021). Comparatively, other cyber event data deidentification approaches identified during the literature review had specific collection, processing or viewing requirements (Menges et al., 2018; Menges et al., 2021; Varanda et al., 2021; Zimmer et al., 2020), creating a barrier to adoption by organizations with existing cyber event monitoring capability. Commercial solutions like ArcSight (Microfocus, 2020) and QRadar (IBM, 2019) offer obfuscation solutions with a similar dependency on specific technology versus the open middleware approach taken by SELD.

An additional component not illustrated in the preceding figures is how FPE is implemented using REST API calls from the Ruby deidentification modules. Many deidentification solutions, including some listed above, require the storage of tokens or cross references for deidentification. An architectural decision was made early in the project to perform the deidentification process inline, requiring only storage of the key set used to encrypt the data provided to the 3DP which also enables timely decryption of deidentified data with the valid key

set. Although the encryption key protection burden on the ODO remains (Article 29 Working Party, 2014), it is considerably less than maintaining a tokenization database with millions of records to address reidentification requirements. Appendix B explores additional technical details related to the deidentification process shown in figure 5.5 as well as several challenges that needed to be overcome.

Detectability Requirements Analysis

One tenet of GDPR and most other privacy regulations is limiting collection to only that which is necessary for the required function, in this case investigating possible cyber attacks. When identifying an intrusion attempt the time sequence and error message content are important but the actual hostname and IP address of the targeted computer are not believed to be essential. What is essential to the security analyst is some indication the IP is an internal host and consistent application of the pseudonym such that as search for all attempted connections to that pseudonymized host or IP could be easily measured using a log analytics platform. This theory on hostname and IP correctness contributing to detection accuracy has not been tested within this project phase. The assessment of security analyst effectiveness identifying cyber intrusions within deidentified data sets is being considered for future research work, therefore detectability testing was limited to functional testing of investigation actions typically performed by a cyber security analyst.

Figures 5.1 and 5.2 earlier in this chapter confirm searching for an individual username within deidentified data is possible and returns the same record count regardless of data source. This activity is the inverse of a standard investigation approach since the analyst will seldom initially know the account name they are looking for. Therefore, a common threat use case, a high number of failed logins from an individual source IP (Murdoch, 2018), will be tested against deidentified Linux authlog data within the 335,527-record set.

Note: *The security analyst is presumed familiar with datatypes within the analytics platform and following a previously vetted investigation process, searching rationale have been omitted for brevity*

Service and Content Specific Search

Locate all failed SSH login events (fig 5.7)

Figure 5.12 Initial search: failed SSH login

Visualize Attack Source and Target

Group by attacker source IP and target hostname (fig 5.8)

Figure 5.13 Grouping data by two dimensions

Refine Existing Search

Restrict failed logon search to internal IP range sources - addition highlighted (fig 5.9)

Figure 5.14 Refine search, limiting to internal source addresses

Group and Visualize Results

Group results to see most targeted host(s) and source IP of potential attacker (fig 5.10)

Figure 5.15 Summarize source and target - most failed SSH logins

Isolated Search by Source IP

Search for all SSH event from source IP 10.14.181.78 and username “FNGV3B” (fig 5.11)

Figure 5.16 Source IP and message content search

The final analyst search confirms that both successful and unsuccessful authentication events are occurring from the same source IP and this does not appear to be malicious behaviour. The search sequence walk-through this section confirms deidentified data can respond the same way in analyst searching activities.

Detailed Operating System Process Monitoring

A known limitation of tracking authentication events is the lack of visibility account actions post authentication. To address this visibility gap, Windows process event command line monitoring was enabled the lab environment to assess monitoring of user behaviour in a deidentified data set, see Appendix C for a more complex investigation using Windows, Linux, and firewall event logs.

Microsoft offers granular auditing on much of the operating system activity, which can be a double-edged visibility sword. For example, enabling auditing for Windows process command lines will generate hundreds-to-thousands of events per host, per day and greater than 90% will be internal operating system processes an analyst must filter out prior starting an investigation. Fig 5.12 confirms the command line detail is captured in the deidentified data, supporting analyst investigation, and a particular reidentification risk, discovered during module development, has also been highlighted.

Figure 5.17 Windows command line auditing, filtered search

This Microsoft audit setting also records the new and parent process names, which along with the command line contain the full path to the files associated with the process. In many cases, one or more of these paths will include an account username. Fig 5.12 confirms this data has been properly deidentified which unfortunately comes at the cost of extra event record processing time and code complexity, redrawing attention to the privacy-utility dilemma each original data processor (ODP) must consider while developing their filtering pipeline. A previous study on developing a GDPR compliant SIEM encountered a similar privacy concern with path information exposing indirect identifiers (Menges et al., 2021), opting to remove the path from the event record detail and discovering the detection confidence of the SIEM was lower across the board (fig 5.13).

Fig. 4 – Comparison of powers of characteristic evidence sets with personal data (blue) and without personal data (black). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Figure 5.18 SIEM detection, with and without user path data (Menges et al., 2021)

When potentially sensitive data appears in a predictable location freeform data extraction deidentification can be reliably programmed. A new challenge is encountered when the command line is subject to administrative syntax preference. Consider the command line opening the Microsoft Terminal Services Client (MSTSC), figure 5.14 shows the process being initiated that will open a dialog box which the administrator populates with a destination machine name or IP address.

Figure 5.19 Command line process without sensitive data

The *mstsc* command also accepts a “-v” parameter followed by the destination host, adding the internal hostname or IP to the command line data. An analyst now only needs to look for the corresponding type 10 logon event and the target hostname has been reidentified, (see Appendix F). Records containing sensitive terms such as original IP ranges, hosts, accounts, or domains can be deleted prior to sharing the data, provided the record loss is within 1-3% since original logging environments experience collection losses as well. Each organization will need to assess their own fidelity loss tolerance knowing a dozen clear text records could lead to reidentification, may be difficult to program for all conditions, and potentially inconsequential within a 100,000-record set.

IP utility Requirement

Using shift ciphers in the deidentification process allows RFC1918 range IP addresses to retain the same prefix, I.E., 10., 192.168. or 172.16/12, while changing the middle portion of the IP network as well as the final host address. The IP pseudonymization section of chapter 4 explains the process in detail and many of the figures in this chapter’s searching examples show populated IP address fields, therefore the requirement to retain the appearance of an IP address in a nearby network has been met. A point of consideration is the IP address data is string value when stored in datafiles, yet searches requiring exclusion or inclusion of an IP range may require some form of custom importing to convert the IP address into an integer. Although there are suspected reidentification weaknesses with the shift cipher approach, a more robust encryption such as the HMAC mutation proposed by (Varanda et al., 2021) results in a data structure that can not be intuitively searched to identify all hosts in a certain network range exhibiting a specific behaviour as demonstrated in figure 5.9.

Some attempts to reverse the shift cipher algorithm were made during development but testing for robust cryptographic protection was not performed within the project. That said, the brute force key space in the smallest RFC1918 network range, 192.168.0.0/16, is more than 64,000 possible addresses while maintaining the close relationship of hosts within each network. It should also be acknowledged that without original IP addresses leaking into the deidentified data a threat agent has no means of validating the which cipher set in the brute force key space corresponds to the original IP range. Finally, even in the event of a processing mistake resulting in a leak, RFC1918 ranges are used globally and could be associated with many different organizations. This concept, originally coined “k-anonymity” (Samarati & Sweeney, 1998) combined with additional protective measures taken to change the source port associated with the communication provide a level of protection that is believed to meet reidentification protection levels defined in GDPR article 25.

Conclusions

The SELD project tested the hypothesis that cyber event data collected from modern systems could be deidentified in a manner that removed quasi-identifiers while still allowing data searching like the actions performed by a security analyst. GDPR guidelines on electronic identifiers were used as criteria for what portions of the cyber event data collected from the lab environment would normally be considered potentially sensitive in an organization and therefore require deidentification.

IP addresses within the RFC1918 ranges, hereafter called “internal IP addresses” were considered quasi-identifiers, as were names of computers, user accounts and authentication domains. Software testing confirmed all fields were successfully deidentified while retaining their original form. For example, a computer host name such as “infsvc09.ymmv.local” was deidentified as “Wi9aWeKr.Mf-9.Y6Xsg”, note the same number of characters between each “.” character delimiter allowing a search for “*.Mf-9.Y6Xsg” to return all the computer hosts associated with that domain. Testing also confirmed IP addresses were deidentified but retained characteristics allowing searching and filtering by network ranges.

Although other cyber event deidentification solutions were identified during the literature review and the software development work, deidentification was often accomplished by pseudonymizing the sensitive fields with alternative data structures such as hashes or tokens. While accomplishing the deidentification goal, the search utility would be reduced compared to the approaches taken by this project. The project choice to use format preserving encryption (FPE) to ensure searchable data elements was not without consideration. The library selected, Python FF3 does meet NIST 800-38-gr1 128-bit block cipher requirements (Schoening, 2019) but due to an earlier revelation of weaknesses in FF3 (Durak & Vaudenay, 2017; Hoang et al., 2019) extreme care and validation were observed during the implementation, including the creation of a key generation tool that avoids the known vulnerability in the encryption tweak input.

The duration of the project did not support the inclusion of testing of how human security analysts would perform identifying intrusions within the deidentified data. Expanding the project to design such a testing environment and engaging security analysts of different skill levels is a priority for future work. One of the main drivers for the project is to provide realistic data from industry sources to be used in cyber security skills training. Although search tests performed on the deidentified data generated in the lab appear to meet this criteria, controlled testing with analysts of varying skill and experience levels is the best way to objectively confirm the usability aspects of this thesis hypothesis.

This project’s current contributions are an extensive literature review into the current state of cyber security skills requirements and data privacy requirements for training data to support that skill development. A conceptual framework was developed to guide other research in this area, particularly those pursuing a modular approach. Although multiple examples were found in the literature of single purpose collection and deidentification solutions, no other opensource project was identified during research that extended an established event collection platform to perform deidentification of selected quasi-identifier fields for multiple log source types.

The source code for the project and a support wiki have been published at <https://github.com/dleeceseld/seld>.

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Appendix A Lab design document

Hardware Considerations

This appendix documents important elements of the testing environment that would be applicable to further experimentation, the audience is assumed to be highly familiar with many aspects of information technology and requiring limited instruction on how to configure software, networking, and physical hardware. Paul Smith’s “Pentesting Industrial Control Systems” provides an excellent step by step guide to setting up many of the elements used in this lab environment (Smith, 2021). As mentioned in chapter two of this thesis, no published standard for a cyber range testing environment was identified, therefore the instruction following is based solely on the author’s experiences building cyber ranges and test labs.

Freely available server virtualization software enables researchers to recreate computer host and networking configurations found in corporate, educational, and industrial environments. A type 1 hypervisor platform such as ProxMox, VMware ESXi or Xen (ProxMox, 2023; VMWare, 2023; Xen Project, n.d.) is recommended due to the significant resource requirements needed by the Elastic environment for deidentification pipelines. An initial investment for at least one used server would be required and can range from 300.00 to 1,500 USD not including software licenses and the ongoing cost of electricity. The lab environment used for the SELD proof-of-concept required approximately 64 GB of ram and slightly less than 1TB of storage (Fig A.1) and a suitable server could be acquired for 400 GBP (Fig A.2).

Figure A.20 ESXi server hosting a lab environment

The screenshot shows an eBay product listing for a Dell PowerEdge R320 server. The listing includes a photograph of the server, its title, a price of GBP 300.00, and various purchase options. The server is described as a 1U server with a six-core processor, 72GB of RAM, and six 600GB hard drives. The listing also includes a return policy and shipping information.

Figure 21 Used server purchase

Used commercial servers are commonly available in a variety of configurations with memory and hard drive being the two primary variables to cost. Type 1 hypervisor software requires very little overhead, so designing a lab or cyber testing range typically comes down to balancing how many systems need to run simultaneously for experimentation and the level of funding available.

As mentioned above, Elastic search deidentification requires more ram and CPU than most of the hosts within a lab environment that would be generating alerts. The Logstash collection appliance should be running during active event generation, but once sufficient data has been collected the generation hosts could be shut down to free up resources for the deidentification pipelines and analytics platform. Elasticsearch storage and Kibana were used for the SELD proof-of-concept, alternative testing platforms like Splunk or QRadar would potentially require some mapping activities, Elasticsearch import pipeline configurations have been included in the project Git Hub (Leece, 2023)

Figure A.22 SELD Proof-of-concept event generation environment

Event Generation Sources

An Active Directory domain was created for the SELD project to allow authentication event collection from both client workstations and servers as well as the central domain controllers. Figure 3 also shows several systems commonly used in networked organization like file servers, data base servers, DNS services and some custom applications, more than 40 unique user accounts were created, and 8 different accounts were used in manual traffic generation actions such mapping network shares, logging into other hosts and internet surfing. A mail system was not implemented because the meta data in the logs was too variable for initial deidentification experiments, but it is slated for future work.

Three RFC1918 network ranges were created using ESXi software defined networking switches, hosts from each network were connected to a specific virtual switch (Fig A.4). A VYOS router appliance (Vyos, 2023) with three interfaces was created to route traffic between networks and out to the internet. Internet bound host traffic was natted behind a single IP with one port forwarding rule within the PFSense (PFSense, 2023) configuration to expose the SFTP server to the internet. Representative networks from all three RFC1918 ranges were used to ensure traffic samples were created to validate SELD IP pseudonymization for each network range was correct.

Figure 23 SELD lab layer 2

Elastic Component Installation

Each researcher will have a preferred approach to creating a test network therefore configuration details are limited to the Logstash pipelines and log collection agent settings. All Elastic components used Ubuntu 20.04.5 LTS server build, table A.1 documents the final resource allocations for each host function, initial estimates were made, and resources increased when performance issues were identified, there was no assessment of minimum requirements.

Table A.1 SELD server component sizing

SELD Elastic Component	System Specifications	Description
Logstash Collector Pipeline	4 GB RAM, 32 GB disk, 4 CPU cores	Dedicated server ready to receive Winlogbeat and TCP Syslog traffic as pipeline is always on, writes daily output files for each source type
ElasticSearch Storage	8 GB RAM, 72 GB disk, 4 CPU cores	A single node document storage and indexing server used for searching
Kibana Search tool	2 GB RAM, 24 GB disk, 2 CPU cores	A HTTP application serving as a proxy between the Elasticsearch storage and an analyst's browser.
Logstash Deidentification Pipeline	8 GB ram, 48 GB disk, 8 CPU cores	The server hosting REST APIs for format preserving

		encryption, the Ruby deidentification modules and both data ingest and Elasticsearch import Logstash configs. Pipelines are started via command line and load from file directories
--	--	---

Software Installation

Primary guidance on Logstash installation for Ubuntu servers is best retrieved from the Elastic website based on the Logstash version selected for use. Version 8.5 was select at the project start and version 8.7 was the recommended version by project end (Elastic, 2023b) . Likewise, the official Elastic guidance was used for both the Elasticsearch and Kibana server installations.

Logstash Network Collector Configuration

On startup the Logstash process looks for a configuration file in `/etc/logstash` or `/etc/logstash/conf.d` but will also accept the `-f` flag followed by a path to the desired configuration file. The file collector configuration file starts Logstash listeners on two tcp ports, 5044 and 514 and each event received through those ports with a metadata element called `type` which is used in conditional logic defining the output file destination for each event. Figure A.5 also highlights a parsing function to determine if the syslog event stream corresponds to RFC5424 format.

```
##### Input section #####
input {
  beats {
    port => 5044
    codec => json
    type => "centralEvtx"
  }
  syslog {
    port => 514
    type => "centralSyslog"
    # Format for 5424 syslog as generated by pfsense 2.6
    grok_pattern => "<{%POSINT:syslogpri}>{%POSINT:version} {%SPACE} {%TIMESTAMP_ISO8601:timestamp}%"
  }
}
```

Figure A.24 Logstash network event collector sample

Despite technically conforming to Syslog RFC3164, different Linux distributions have slight format variations which was addressed by testing for an array of possible regular expressions. Figure A.6 also highlights the use of the Logstash mutate feature which can act on event metadata such as removing or adding a tag as well as changing content within the event itself, (removing an extra newline in the parsed records in this case).

```

# Need to deal with multiple syslog variants, grok pattern in syslog accepts one string so put
# all remaining possible patterns in an array and remove grok parsing failure tag if successful.
filter {
  if "_grokparsefailure_sysloginput" in [tags] {
    grok {
      match => {
        "message" => [
          "%{SYSLOGTIMESTAMP:timestamp} %{SPACE} %{SYSLOG
          "%<%(POSINT:[log][syslog][facility][code]:int)> %{SYSLOGTIMESTAMP:timestamp} %{SPACE} %{SYSLOG
          "%<%(POSINT:[log][syslog][facility][code]:int)> %{SYSLOGTIMESTAMP:timestamp} %{SPACE} %{SYSLOG
          "%<%(POSINT:[log][syslog][facility][code]:int)> %{SYSLOGTIMESTAMP:timestamp} %{SPACE} %{SYSLOG
        ]
      }
    }
  }
}

# Remove grok parse failure tags for pattern matches in the follow on filter,
# allows monitoring initial ingest
if [rfc3164msg_linux] {
  mutate { add_tag => "rfc3164_linux" }
  mutate { remove_tag => ["_grokparsefailure_sysloginput"] }
  mutate { gsub => ["message", "[\\n]", ""] }
}

```

Figure 25 Logstash conditional regex and mutate function

Logstash is a very full featured product with much more information than can be covered in a technical appendix. Fortunately, a great deal of free training available on the internet and the vendor's documentation is extensive, the SELD release code is also generously commented.

Logstash Deidentification Pipeline Configuration

The network collector pipeline is intended to run as a service to receive events anytime they occur, conversely, on startup, the deidentification pipelines search a file directory for specific file names and once processing is completed the pipeline shuts down. In thesis chapter 4 there is mention of combining both collection and deidentification into a real-time workflow, this would be a welcome enhancement option but is not currently implemented. Figure A.7 shows all files beginning with named linux3164.log will be processed by this pipeline, all other files will be ignored.

*It is worth noting that an application directory structure using **"/opt/seld"** as the top level location was used within configuration files that needed to reference paths. Changes to path locations should not affect the code operation if all related programs are identified and changed. (See the software repository installation wiki for more detail).*

PFsense Firewall Event Deidentified Output Generation

Due to the unique and often nuanced message content within the Linux authlog numerous format clauses must be included in the output filtering section. The comma separated value structure within the Pfsense event records allows for both efficient deidentification and rewriting the deidentified event to an output file. Figure A.9 shows a single formatted output syntax works for all PFSense firewall events which also contributes to faster data processing.

```
##### File output section #####
if "fwsyslog_host" in [tags] and "fwsyslog_FWEvent" in [tags] {
  file { path => "/opt/seld/deidentlogs/deident-fwsyslog_rfc5424.log"
    # need to recreate the formatting based on extracted fields, event api doesn't rewrite message field directly (how inconvenient)
    codec => line { format => '<%(pri)>%(version) %[[event][created]] %[[host][name]] %[[program][name]] %[[program][pid]] - - %[[rule][FWEvent]]' }
  }
}
# End of output filter
}
```

Figure A.28 PFSense events written to an output file

Windows Event Log Event Deidentified Output Generation

Like the PFSense example above, converting the proprietary Windows XML output to JSON lines then updating field values within each JSON document allows a single processing filter to address all Windows Event Log records. Figure A.10 shows the entire JSON document contained within that variable %[[winlog]] is written as a single line to the output file named in the path statement. The line codec applies a newline to the end of each record written, returning the output to it's original JSON Lines format, with deidentified data.

```
##### File output section #####
if "_json_parsed_success" in [tags] {
  file { path => "/opt/seld/deidentlogs/deident-windowsevt.json"
    codec => line { format => '%[[winlog]]' }
  }
}
# End of output filter
}
```

Figure A.29 Windows Events rewritten to JSON Lines output

Log Forwarding Requirements

Winlogbeat Configuration

Like Logstash, Elasticsearch and Kibana, the most reliable reference for installing the Winlogbeat agent is the Elastic website (Elastic, 2023e). It should be noted that the default agent installation will not collect the XML event data, therefore some modification of the YAML configuration file is required prior to sending events to the Logstash network collector. Figure A.11 highlights the use of an Elastic module built into Elastic that write the XML content into a new field which can then be processed in later stages of the pipeline (Elastic, 2023a). A code review of the Logstash network collection configuration file will confirm the XML data field is converted to JSON and directly written to a file with no additional modifications required. The

ability to use built in features from the Elastic suite to resolve technical issues without a great deal of extra programming reaffirms the choice to implement SELD within an existing technology stack.

```
processors:
  - decode_xml_wineventlog:
    field: event.original
    target_field: winlog

winlogbeat.event_logs:
  - name: Application
    include_xml: true
    ignore_older: 168h

  - name: System
    include_xml: true

  - name: Security
    include_xml: true
    ignore_older: 168h

  - name: Windows PowerShell
    include_xml: true
    ignore_older: 168h
    event_id: 400, 403, 600, 800

  - name: Microsoft-Windows-PowerShell/Operational
    include_xml: true
    ignore_older: 168h
```

Figure A.30 Winlogbeat XML processor customization

Linux Syslog Configuration

Log forwarding is built into BSD syslog protocol, therefore there is nothing to install on Linux servers, just a configuration file modification. All Linux distributions used in the SELD lab environment were running the rsyslog daemon which supports forwarding event records over TCP streams (Gerhards, 2008). Figure A.12 shows the auth and authpriv facilities are written to a file /var/log/auth.log and forwarded to an IP address, 10.5.100.219. The two @@ characters in front of the IP inform the rsyslog daemon to use TCP as the network transport protocol rather than UDP as originally defined in the RFCs.

```
# First some standard log files: log by facility
auth,authpriv.*                @@10.50.100.219
auth,authpriv.*                /var/log/auth.log
*.*;auth,authpriv.none         -/var/log/syslog
local5.*                        -/var/log/cwdmon.log
```

Figure A.31 Rsyslog configuration change required for network event collection

PFSense Syslog Configuration

Since PFSense is firewall management application running on an hardened version of BSD the syslog daemon is already configured to collect logs, forwarding is done by modifying the system settings using the application’s HTML-based management interface (Fig A.13). Unexpectedly the default RFC3164 format by PFSense does not include the hostname in the forwarded event records. In a larger environment with many firewalls, understanding which firewall is reporting the event is very important to an investigator because it helps identify the location and direction of the traffic being reported on. Changing the default logging format to RFC5424 resolves the missing hostname data.

Enable Remote Logging Send log messages to remote syslog server

Source Address This option will allow the logging daemon to bind to a single IP address, rather than all IP addresses. If a single IP is must all be of that IP type. To mix IPv4 and IPv6 remote syslog servers, bind to all interfaces.

NOTE: If an IP address cannot be located on the chosen interface, the daemon will bind to all addresses.

IP Protocol This option is only used when a non-default address is chosen as the source above. This option only expresses a pr selected type is not found on the chosen interface, the other type will be tried.

Remote log servers

Remote Syslog Contents

- Everything
- System Events
- Firewall Events
- DNS Events (Resolver/unbound, Forwarder/dnsmasq, filterdns)
- DHCP Events (DHCP Daemon, DHCP Relay, DHCP Client)

Figure A.32 PFSense Firewall Event Forwarding

Third-Party Software and Libraries

Table A.2 documents the Linux operating system used on all four component servers as well as the software packages and supporting libraries needed to implement the solution. Software versions were considered stable at the beginning of the project, no upgrades beyond security patches were installed during the project development cycle to ensure consistency within the environment.

Table A.2 SELD Platform Supporting Third-Party Software

Software Name	Function	Software Installation Source
ElasticSearch 8.5.3	Cyber event record storage in searchable document format	https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/welcome-to-elastic/8.5/stack-components.html Installed as Debian package: https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/elasticsearch/reference/current/deb.html
Kibana 8.5.3	Search and visualization interface to analyze Cyber event records stored in Elastic search	Installed as Debian package:

		https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/elasticsearch/reference/current/deb.html
Logstash 8.5.3	Cyber event record processing pipeline software, used for collection, deidentification processing and demonstration of log file import by third party data processor	Installed as Debian package: https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/elasticsearch/reference/current/deb.html
Winlogbeat	A Windows OS specific EventLog collection agent	https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/beats/winlogbeat/current/winlogbeat-installation-configuration.html https://www.elastic.co/downloads/past-releases/winlogbeat-8-5-3
Jruby 9.3.10	The Ruby language ported to Java. Installed by default when Logstash is installed with the bundled JDK package (recommended approach). Version included to support a dedicated Jruby module development server if needed	https://www.jruby.org/download
FF3 1.0.1	Format preserving encryption module meeting NIST 800-38G requirements	https://pypi.org/project/ff3/
Flask 2.2.2	Python framework library for implementing small HTTP applications, required for the REST API needed for Format Preserving Encryption	https://pypi.org/project/Flask/2.2.2/
Ubuntu 20.04.5 LTS	Linux server platform used for all components including raw log collection, deidentification, Elasticsearch storage and the Kibana search platform.	https://old-releases.ubuntu.com/releases/20.04.5/

Appendix B Event Record/Logfile Processing Details

The Windows and Linux operating systems record similar types of events such as authentication, privilege use and process execution but viewing mechanisms content within records varies considerably, as illustrated in figures B.1 and B.2. Viewing is only the start of the differences, and much of the project effort was dedicated to developing the parsing approaches required to identify, extract, and replace the potentially sensitive fields identified during the SELD framework data requirements phase.

```
dleece@infdev28:/opt/seld/rawlogs/analyzed$ grep -i cron linux3164.log-2023-04-10
<85>Apr 9 18:09:53 infdev19 sudo: ychaney : TTY=pts/2 ; PWD=/opt/appdata/transfers ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/usr/sbin/cron -l
<86>Apr 9 18:17:01 infdev19 CRON[65567]: pam_unix(cron:session): session closed for user root
<86>Apr 9 18:17:01 infsvc57 CRON[17850]: pam_unix(cron:session): session opened for user root by (uid=0)
<86>Apr 9 18:17:01 infdev19 CRON[65567]: pam_unix(cron:session): session opened for user root by (uid=0)
<86>Apr 9 18:17:01 infsvc57 CRON[17850]: pam_unix(cron:session): session closed for user root
<86>Apr 9 18:17:01 infsec21 CRON[62835]: pam_unix(cron:session): session opened for user root by (uid=0)
<86>Apr 9 18:17:01 infsec21 CRON[62835]: pam_unix(cron:session): session closed for user root
<86>Apr 9 18:17:01 infsvc14 CRON[65340]: pam_unix(cron:session): session opened for user root by (uid=0)
```

Figure B.1 Searching Linux authlog for scheduled process execution

The screenshot displays the Windows Security Event Viewer interface. At the top, it shows 'Security' with 193,015 events. A filter is applied: 'Log: Security; Source: ; Event ID: 4688; Date Range: From 1/22/2023 4:14:51 PM to 1/22/2023 5:14:51 PM. Number of events: 87'. Below the filter, a table lists several 'Audit Success' events from Microsoft Windows security auditing, all with Event ID 4688 and Task Category 'Process Creation'. The detailed view for event 4688 is shown below, titled 'Event 4688, Microsoft Windows security auditing'. It includes a 'General' tab with the following information:

- Message:** A new process has been created.
- Creator Subject:** Security ID: SYSTEM, Account Name: INFVC09S, Account Domain: YMMV, Logon ID: 0x3E7
- Target Subject:** Security ID: LOCAL SERVICE, Account Name: LOCAL SERVICE, Account Domain: NT AUTHORITY, Logon ID: 0x3E5
- Process Information:** New Process ID: 0x13e4, New Process Name: C:\Windows\System32\wbem\WmiPrvSE.exe, Token Elevation Type: %%1936, Mandatory Label: Mandatory Label\System Mandatory Level, Creator Process ID: 0x300, Creator Process Name: C:\Windows\System32\svchost.exe, Process Command Line:
- Log Name:** Security
- Source:** Microsoft Windows security, Logged: 1/22/2023 4:31:23 PM
- Event ID:** 4688, Task Category: Process Creation
- Level:** Information, Keywords: Audit Success
- User:** N/A, Computer: infsvc09.ymmv.local
- OpCode:** Info
- More Information:** [Event Log Online Help](#)

Figure B.2 Viewing Windows process creation events

Record Field Value Identification and Extraction

Applying the deidentification process to a given cyber event record can be summarized in three steps:

- Extract all potentially sensitive fields from cyber event record,
- For each field, determine if sensitive and apply applicable deidentification method for the specific data type,
- Replace each extracted sensitive field with the deidentified data leaving all other record elements as is.

Although conceptually simple, the wide variation in the structure and syntax of the various record types dictates the extraction and replacement process must be customized for each. Once extracted the data within the field values tends to be consistent therefore the deidentification processes such as modifying IP addresses with shift ciphers and applying format preserving encryption can utilize common software modules. This modular functionality has been implemented via several script files written in the Ruby language, a practice recommended by Elastic for complicated event field data processing. As each event was processed the SELD pipelines used conditional logic such as a specific event type or metadata tag to determine which Ruby script file would be used to process the event as well as the specific field data values to be passed as parameters to the processing module (Fig B.3).

```

filter{
  if "winevt_user" in [tags]{
    ruby {
      path => "/opt/seld/conf/modules/acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb"
      script_params => {
        "tunamefield" => "[winlog][event_data][TargetUserName]"
        "sunamefield" => "[winlog][event_data][SubjectUserName]"
        "tsnamefield" => "[winlog][event_data][TargetServerName]"
        "tinfofield" => "[winlog][event_data][TargetInfo]"
        "tounamefield" => "[winlog][event_data][TargetOutboundUserName]"
        "svcnamefield" => "[winlog][event_data][ServiceName]"
        "samnamefield" => "[winlog][event_data][SamAccountName]"
      }
    }
  }
}

# Windows Event Logs may have more than one user or domain SID defined in event data,
# need to include the top level json object in the event data path
filter{
  if "winevt_sid" in [tags]{
    ruby {
      path => "/opt/seld/conf/modules/sid_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb"
      script_params => {
        "tgtusidfield" => "[winlog][event_data][TargetUserSid]"
      }
    }
  }
}

```

Figure B.3 Logstash conditional processing examples

Figure B.3 provides some insight into one of the complexity issues encountered when processing Windows event logs. The Windows event log API uses a variable length array of key value pairs called “event_data” to enable different records to include the fields logged for that specific event type in a consistent fashion for further processing. During the project seven different field names were identified that could contain a sensitive account name, therefore requiring assessment for deidentification, but depending on the event type a given field may or may not exist. To improve reusability of the Ruby modules and potentially pipeline performance, each parameter was tested for null value when the event is passed to the Ruby module. When field parameters were not null the parameter value was passed to a method within the module as shown in figure B4.

```

def filter(event)
  # Almost all Log sources will have at least one account name recorded,
  tgtuname = event.get(@thistuname)
  subuname = event.get(@thissubuname)
  tgtsname = event.get(@thistsname)
  tgtinfo = event.get(@thistinfo)
  svcname = event.get(@thissvcname)
  tgtouname = event.get(@thistouname)
  samname = event.get(@thissamname)

  # Ignore all dash values and empty fields.
  # -- target username -----
  if !tgtuname.nil? && tgtuname.size() > 1
    deidenttgtname = getencacct(tgtuname)
    event.set(@thistuname, deidenttgtname)
  end
  # -- subject username -----
  if !subuname.nil? && subuname.size() > 1
    deidentsubname = getencacct(subuname)
    event.set(@thissubuname, deidentsubname)
  end
  # -- service username -----
  if !svcname.nil? && svcname.size() > 1

```

Figure B4 Ruby module testing Logstash event API inputs

Windows event log records are stored in a binary XML format which can be converted to a JSON document when Logstash receives the message, creating a series of key value pairs for each event shown in the example below.

```

{"computer_name": "infsvc09.ymmv.local", "process": {"pid": 4, "thread": {"id": 3280}}, "keywords": ["Audit
Success"], "level": "information", "channel": "Security", "event_data": {"MandatoryLabel": "S-1-16-
16384", "ParentProcessName": "C:\\Windows\\System32\\svchost.exe", "NewProcessId": "0xff4", "TokenElevationType
": "%1936", "SubjectLogonId": "0x3e7", "NewProcessName": "C:\\Windows\\System32\\wbem\\WmiPrvSE.exe", "TargetLo
gonId": "0x3e4", "CommandLine": "C:\\Windows\\system32\\wbem\\wmiprvse.exe -secured -
Embedding", "SubjectUserName": "INFSVC09$", "SubjectDomainName": "YMMV", "TargetUserName": "INFSVC09$", "ProcessI
d": "0x310", "TargetDomainName": "YMMV", "SubjectUserSid": "S-1-5-18", "TargetUserSid": "S-1-0-0"},

"message": "A new process has been created.
\n\nCreator Subject: \n\nSecurity ID: \t\tS-1-5-18\n\tAccount
Name: \t\tINFSVC09$\n\tAccount Domain: \t\tYMMV\n\tLogon ID: \t\t0x3E7\n\nTarget Subject: \n\nSecurity
ID: \t\tS-1-0-0\n\tAccount Name: \t\tINFSVC09$\n\tAccount Domain: \t\tYMMV\n\tLogon ID: \t\t0x3E4\n\nProcess
Information: \n\nNew Process ID: \t\t0xff4\n\tNew Process
Name: \t\tC:\\Windows\\System32\\wbem\\WmiPrvSE.exe\n\tToken Elevation Type: \t\t%1936\n\tMandatory
Label: \t\tS-1-16-16384\n\nCreator Process ID: \t\t0x310\n\nCreator Process
Name: \t\tC:\\Windows\\System32\\svchost.exe\n\nProcess Command
Line: \t\tC:\\Windows\\system32\\wbem\\wmiprvse.exe -secured -Embedding\n\nToken Elevation Type indicates the
type of token that was assigned to the new process in accordance with User Account Control policy.
\n\nType
1 is a full token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. A full token is only used if User
Account Control is disabled or if the user is the built-in Administrator account or a service
account.
\n\nType 2 is an elevated token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. An elevated token
is used when User Account Control is enabled and the user chooses to start the program using Run as
administrator. An elevated token is also used when an application is configured to always require
administrative privilege or to always require maximum privilege, and the user is a member of the
Administrators group.
\n\nType 3 is a limited token with administrative privileges removed and

```



```

{"rex04688": "(^A new process[\\w\\W+]?)Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)\\s++Account\\s++Name:
{"rex04688-1": "^A new process.+?Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)?\\s++Account\\s++Name:\\s++(
{"rex04688-2": "^A\\s++new\\s++\\process.+?Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)\\s++.+?Name:\\s
{"rex04688-3": "^\\w:\\\\Users\\\\\\\\([~$\\w_\\. -]+)?\\\\\\\\(.++)$"}
{"rex04688-31": "^\\w:\\\\Users\\\\\\\\([~$\\w_\\. -]+)?\\\\\\\\(.++)$"}
{"rex04688-32": "^\\w:\\\\Users\\\\\\\\([~$\\w_\\. -]+)?\\\\\\\\(.++)$"}
{"rex14776": "^.+?validate\\s++the\\s++credentials.+Logon\\s++Account:\\s++([$-\\.\\w@]+)?.+?t
{"rex14625": "^An\\s++account\\s++failed\\s++.+?Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)?\\s++.+?Logc
{"rex14625-1": "^An\\s++account\\s++failed.+?Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)?\\s++Acc.+?ame:
{"rex14720": "^A\\s++user.+?created.+?Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)?\\s++Account\\s++Name:
{"rex14722": "^A\\s++user.+?enabled.+?Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)?\\s++.+?Name:\\s+(\\S
{"rex14724": "^An\\s++attempt.+?reset.+?password.+?Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)?\\s++Acce
{"rex14726": "^A\\s++user.+?deleted.+?Security\\s++ID:\\s+(S[-\\d]++)?\\s++Account\\s++Name:

```

Figure B.6 Windows EventLog message parsing regular expression patterns

Although the Windows Event Log message field contains free form data, the values are derived from the structure event fields and applied to a templated message structure. The Linux authlog is also free form but without the benefit of an event identifier to predefine the expected structure of the data within the message. Thesis chapter 4 explained how in lieu of a specific identifier the process name extracted from the structured portion of a syslog message can be used to limit the regular expressions tested for a given process. Unfortunately, the process name filtering is far less granular than the Windows Event IDs resulting in many possible regular expressions (regex) needing to be tested (Fig B.7).

```

filter {
  if "authlog_sshd" in [tags] {
    grok{ patterns_dir => ["/opt/seld/conf/patterns"] match => {'logdata' => '%{SSHAUTHIVU}'} add_tag => "ssh authentication-ivu" }
    grok{ patterns_dir => ["/opt/seld/conf/patterns"] match => {'logdata' => '%{SSHAUTHIVU0}'} add_tag => "ssh authentication-ivu0" }
    grok{ patterns_dir => ["/opt/seld/conf/patterns"] match => {'logdata' => '%{SSHAUTHIVU1}'} add_tag => "ssh authentication-ivu1" }
    grok{ patterns_dir => ["/opt/seld/conf/patterns"] match => {'logdata' => '%{SSHAUTHDU}'} add_tag => "ssh authentication-du" }
    grok{ patterns_dir => ["/opt/seld/conf/patterns"] match => {'logdata' => '%{SSHAUTHRST}'} add_tag => "ssh authentication-rst" }
    grok{ patterns_dir => ["/opt/seld/conf/patterns"] match => {'logdata' => '%{SSHAUTHRST2}'} add_tag => "ssh authentication-rst2" }
  }
}

```

Figure B.7 Conditional testing message field with regular expressions

Like the Windows message field parsing, the Linux regex patterns are labeled and stored in a file. Unlike the Windows message field parsing, which required more than 1000 lines of custom Ruby code, the Linux pipeline can take advantage of the grok regex parser built into the Logstash platform. Upon a successful grok match named field values are extracted from the freeform string using the group method implemented in most regex libraries. The existence of these fields can then be tested for to define additional metadata tags as shown in (Fig. B.8). The assignment of the metadata tag confirming a key field such as a source IP can form the basis of a third conditional test that assigns multiple field values from the event to specific parameters in the corresponding Ruby module (Fig. B.9).

```

# script based, define the address field to be parsed by the Ruby script
filter {
  if [source.ip] or [source_host]{
    mutate{
      | add_tag => "valid_src"
    }
  }
  if [user.name] {
    mutate{
      | add_tag => "valid_uname"
    }
  }
  if [host.name] {
    mutate{
      | add_tag => "valid_compname"
    }
  }
}

```

Figure B.8 Addition Linux meta data tagging based on field existence

```

# When there is a valid IP address in the logs, proceed with the ruby module to t
if "valid_src" in [tags] {
  ruby {
    path => "/opt/seld/conf/modules/ip_port_name_deident_ecs-v1.rb"
    script_params => {
      "ipaddressfield" => "source.ip"
      "portnumberfield" => "source.port"
      "hostnamefield" => "host.name"
      "usernamefield" => "user.name"
      "sourcehostnamefield" => "source.host.name"
      "source_hostfield" => "source_host"
    }
  }
}

```

Figure B.9 Parameter values directed to custom Ruby module upon conditional tag existence

Field value extraction from PFSense firewall records benefited from a well-defined record structure for the firewall rule event portion of the syslog message. Although the RFC5424 specification treats the message field as free form the PFSense development team write that freeform message as comma delimited string of values. Figure B.10 shows only two pre-processing filters are required for PFSense events, assigning the firewall event time to the Logstash record timestamp and passing the entire rule event field value to a Ruby module. Within the Ruby module the comma delimited data is split into an array with a single method call and array elements are then passed to other modules for deidentification processing (Fig. B.11). Fortunately the PFSense developers have predefined locations within the rule event data making extraction of a value like the destination IP within the event straight forward because it is always index 19.

```

# Correct the timestamp - PFS sense uses 8601 format with microsecond precision, Logstash truncates to milli
filter {
  if [event][created] {
    date{
      match => ["[event][created]", "ISO8601"]
      target => "@timestamp"
      add_tag => "timestamp_original"
    }
  }
}

filter{
  if "fwsyslog_host" in [tags] and "fwsyslog_FWEvent" in [tags] {
    ruby {
      path => "/opt/seld/conf/modules/ip_port_name_deident-pfsfw.rb"
      script_params => {
        "hostnamefield" => "[host][name]"
        "ruleeventfield" => "[rule][FWEvent]"
      }
    }
  }
}

```

Figure B.10 PFSense requires minimal pre-processing

```

# Extract IP and port info from the rule data and deidentifiy as needed
def deidentifyruleeventdata(ruleevtcsv)
  fwrearray=ruleevtcsv.split(',')
  # Deal with source IP and port
  if testiprange(fwrearray[18])
    deidentsrcip=deidentifyipdata(fwrearray[18],@sitekeyset)
    deidentsrcport=deidentifyportdata(fwrearray[20],@sitekeyset)
    fwrearray[18]=deidentsrcip
    fwrearray[20]=deidentsrcport
  else
    deidentsrcport=deidentifyportdata(fwrearray[20],@sitekeyset)
    fwrearray[20]=deidentsrcport
  end
  # test destination ip, destination port should remain original
  if testiprange(fwrearray[19])
    #puts("deident target side:" + fwrearray[19])
    deidentdstip=deidentifyipdata(fwrearray[19],@sitekeyset)
    fwrearray[19]=deidentdstip
  end
  return fwrearray.join(',')
end

```

Figure B.11 Ruby module splitting CSV record into array

Addressing Complex Unique Identifiers

Both the Linux and Windows operating systems (OS) identify users with an account name and a unique numeric identifier is also associated with the account, typically based on the order in which the account was created. To maintain unique identification across an entire domain the

Windows operating system generates a globally unique number called a security identifier (SID). In addition to globally unique identifiers for both domains and the accounts within that domain the Windows OS also includes more than 80 universal identifiers associated with core accounts within the operating system, (table B1).

Table B1 SID Examples and Usage

Security Identifier Type	
Well known: Occuring on all Windows OS	S-1-15-2-1
Domain SID: Globally unique (highlighted)	S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885
Account SID: Domain unique (highlighted)	S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1115

The domain SID is randomly generated during the creation of a Windows Active Directory domain and bears no relationship to the domain name defined during setup and is therefore not attributable to an organization on its own. Although the GUID prevents direct reidentification it is the globally unique nature that creates a reidentification risk through external data publication. While not a direct requirement for GDPR article 32 compliance, the SELD project has taken measures to address foreseeable reidentification risks such as public information that can be relinked to a deidentified dataset. Figure B.12 shows the domain name and SID, likely inadvertently included as part of code documentation, which can be linked back to an organization by analyzing the profile of the person posting the code. Admittedly the adversary would also need to be in possession of deidentified data from this same domain, a very unlikely scenario considering the test nature of the domain and the age of the posting, this may not be the case for a government department or large company enlisting the services of a third-party security or research organization.

Figure B.12 SID exposure leading to organization reidentification.

To address reidentification risk due to system configuration data being publically posted in a support forum or blog, the domain and user portions of the SID are extracted and modified using format preserving encryption (FPE). Figure B.13 confirms the GUID 2346142638-329485983-1959203885 has been encrypted as 0334535618-953786910-8880575821 but two account ID

values associated with built-in OS accounts generate many predictable events allowing the original clear text values to be inferred from the cipher text and reducing the time to crack encryption keys. To combat this threat the user ID values 502 and 1000 are not included in SID data input for the encryption function but appended to the encrypted result as shown in the code sample below (Fig. B.14)

```

{
  "@timestamp" => 2023-02-08T12:55:23.939Z,
  "winlog" => {
    "level" => "information",
    "message" => "A Kerberos service ticket was renewed. Account Information: Account Name: Yb-_wt3Rurj@PKMt.Mxofq Additional Information: Service Name: krbtgt Service ID: S-1-5-21-3692334535618-953786913692-8883692575821-736922893 Network Interface: 23692 Additional Information: Ticket Options: 3692x13692369236922 Ticket Encryption Type: 3692x12 Ticket options: 23692.",
    "process" => {
      "thread" => {
        "id" => 2292
      }, "pid" => 616
    },
    "channel" => "Security",
    "record_id" => 1130490,
    "task" => "Kerberos Service Ticket Operations",
    "opcode" => "Info",
    "time_created" => "2023-02-08T12:55:23.939Z",
    "computer_name" => "DURSNEV4.MF-9.Y6Xsg",
    "provider_guid" => "{54849625-5478-4994-A5BA-3E3B0328C30D}",
    "event_data" => {
      "IpPort" => 3692,
      "ServiceSid" => "S-1-5-21-0334535618-953786910-8880575821-702893",
      "TargetUserName" => "Yb-_wt3Rurj@PKMt.Mxofq",
      "ServiceName" => "krbtgt",
      "IpAddress" => ":1",
      "TargetDomainName" => "PKMt.Mxofq",
      "TicketEncryptionType" => "0x12",
      "TicketOptions" => "0x10002"
    },
    "keywords" => [
      [0] "Audit Success"
    ],
    "provider_name" => "Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing",
    "outcome" => "success",
    "event_id" => "4770"
  }
}

```

Figure B.13 SID domain and user identifier encryption

```

# Special method for encrypting "-" delimited digit strings like SIDs while retaining "-"
def encdddigit(dddigit):
    encdddlist = []
    dddlist = dddigit.split("-")
    for elem in dddlist:
        # Don't encrypt kerberos or local admin
        if elem == "1000" or elem == "502":
            encdddlist.append(elem)
        else:
            tdelem = testelemdigit(elem)
            encdddlist.append(fpenumonly.encrypt(tdelem))
    #
    encdddstr = "-".join(encdddlist)
    return encdddstr

```

Figure B.14 Encryption exclusion for well know accounts.

SELD Deidentification Software List

The following modules, configuration files, scripts and supporting files, created specifically for the SELD project are included in the initial code release, publically available through the following GIT hub repository <https://github.com/dleeceseld>. Table B2 summarizes the inputs and supporting services needed to perform the deidentification processes on the various types of event data with extensive comments in code modules for those needing to perform code assessment prior to use.

Table B2 Custom Software Developed for SELD project

Software Component Name	Function(s) Performed	Supporting Input data & Services
acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb	Deidentification of account name data contained within Windows EventLog records	FPE REST API: <i>encatdelimalpha</i> winreserved_list.txt winsvcs_list.txt
cmduserdata_deident-winevt-ecs-v2.rb	Analyze Windows OS command file paths or account home directories and extract username or company name fields while excluding known operating system locations and accounts to deter FPE cracking	FPE REST API: <i>encatdelimalpha</i> winreserved_list.txt winsvcs_list.txt sensitivenames_list.txt
domname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb	Analyze field values associated with domain names for FPE encryption, excluding known OS specific domains	FPE REST API: <i>encdotdelumalpha</i> winreserved_list.txt domain_list.txt
filepath_deident.rb	Analyze Linux OS command file paths or account home directories and extract username or company name fields while excluding known operating system locations and accounts to deter FPE cracking	FPE REST API: <i>encname sensitivepaths [in-code-array]</i>
groupmodify_deident-winevt.rb	Extract and encrypt sensitive field values from Windows events related to group membership modification	FPE REST API: <i>encatdelimalpha</i> FPE REST API: <i>encdotdelimalpha</i> FPE REST API: <i>encdashdelimdigit</i> winreserved_list.txt winsvcs_list.txt

hostname_deident-winevt-ecs-v2.rb	Extract and encrypt three different Windows EventLog fields associated with computer names	FPE REST API: <i>encdotdelimalpha</i>
ip_port_name-deident_ecs-v1.rb	Extract and apply shift ciphers to RFC1918 IP addresses and source ports identified in Linux authlogs. Extract and encrypt hostnames reporting the authlog events	sitekeyset.yml linwellknown_list.txt FPE REST API: <i>encname</i> FPE REST API: <i>encdotdelimalpha</i>
ip_port_name_deident-pfsfw.rb	Extract and apply shift ciphers to RFC1918 IP addresses and source ports identified in PFSense firewall logs. Extract and encrypt firewall hostnames within each record	sitekeyset.yml FPE REST API: <i>encdotdelimalpha</i>
ip64port_deident-winevt-v2.rb	Extract and apply shift ciphers to RFC1918 IP addresses and source ports identified in Windows EventLog records	sitekeyset.yml
msg_sans-format.v2.rb	Extract and encrypt all sensitive field data from the Windows EventLog message field. (Includes copies of IP, hostname, SID, domain, and account name deidentification modules	FPE REST API: <i>encatdelimalpha</i> FPE REST API: <i>encdotdelimalpha</i> FPE REST API: <i>encdashdelimdigit</i> winreserved_list.txt winsvcs_list.txt winrex.jsonl domain_list.txt sitekeyset.yml
multiuser_deident.rb	Extract and encrypt additional usernames identified in a small number of Linux auth logs, typically SUDO related, while avoiding encryption of well known accounts like root	FPE REST API: <i>encname</i> linwellknown_list.txt
name_only_deident.rb	Extract and encrypt account and host names from Linux authlogs that do not contain an IP address	FPE REST API: <i>encname</i> FPE REST API: <i>encdotdelimalpha</i> linwellknown_list.txt
psoper_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb	Extract and encrypt account, SID and domain from PowerShell operational logs, avoiding encryption of well-known values for each	FPE REST API: <i>encatdelimalpha</i> FPE REST API: <i>encdotdelimalpha</i>

		FPE REST API: <i>encdashdelimdigit</i> domain_list.txt winreserved_list.txt winsvcs_list.txt
sid_deident-winevet_ecs-v2.rb	Encrypt domain and user SID values, ignore well-known OS SIDS	FPE REST API: <i>encdashdelimdigit</i>
sudocmd_deident.rb	Extract and encrypt account names from SUDO commands and home drive paths	FPE REST API: <i>encname sensitivepaths [in-code-array]</i>
Ruby Module Support Inputs		
FPE REST API: fpeapi-account-local5020.py fpeapi-host-local5021.py fpeapi-sid-local5022.py fpeapi-domain-local5023.py fpeapi-account-local5030.py fpeapi-host-local5031.py fpeapi-sid-local5032.py fpeapi-domain-local5033.py fpeapi-all-5042.py	An HTTP REST service using the Python FF3 library to apply format preserving encryption to both alphanumeric and digit only data Instantiated as standalone flask python scripts running on localhost with different ports to improve performance API supports multiple function calls to address the different possible data input formats and avoid encrypting defined delimiter values like “.-@” Fpeapi-all instance listens on a network IP address and can be used to reidentify FPE encrypted hostnames	keyfile.txt
domain_list.txt	A list of domains used by the organization as well as optional strings like computer naming convention prefixes, EG., <i>desktop[1,2,n], devsrv[...]</i>	
linwellknown_list.txt	Common Linux OS and application names for exemption from encryption, also includes a selection of names commonly used in brute force credential guessing attacks	

sitekeyset.yml	The numbers and boolean values used for IP shift cipher encryption	
winreserved_list.txt	Common Windows OS account and group names for exemption from encryption	
winrex.jsonl	Custom regular expression patterns used for Windows EventLog message field parsing	
Winsvcs_list.txt	Prefixes for common OS account names that should not be encrypted like DWM-[1,2,n] (default window manager)	
Logstash Pipeline Configuration Files		
Is_Winlogbeat-Syslog_json1-v1-2.conf	Raw real-time event collection over network from Winlogbeat agents, Syslog RFC3164 and RFC5424 sources. Output files are date stamped, rotate every 24 hours and confirm to Syslog or JSONL formats.	winlogbeat-decodexml.yml
Is_FWSyslog-RFC5424-ControlTesting-Elastic_output.conf	Import original PFSense firewall logs, apply ECS field mapping were applicable and output to Elasticsearch (Use for comparing original and deidentified datasets)	
Is_FWSyslog-RFC5424-Elastic_output.conf	Import deidentified PFSense firewall logs, apply ECS field mapping were applicable and output to Elasticsearch	
Is_FWSyslog-RFC5424-v1-2.conf	Main log deidentification pipeline for processing PFSense log files	
Is_LinuxAuth_Deident-syslog3164-fileoutput-v1-2.conf	Main log deidentification pipeline for processing Linux authlog files	
Is_LinuxAuth-Deident-Elastic_output.conf	Import deidentified Linux authlog files, apply ECS field mapping were applicable and output to Elasticsearch	
Is_WindowsEVT-JSON-v1-2.conf	Main log deidentification pipeline for processing Windows JSONL files	

Is_WinEVT-ControlTesting-Elastic_output.conf	Import test JSONL file, apply ECS field mapping were applicable and output to Elasticsearch (Use for comparing original and deidentified datasets)	
Is_WinEVT-ControlTesting-JSONL_output.conf	Import original Window JSONL files, drop records not processed by deidentification pipeline, output to test JSONL file, (use to ensure similar data set for test comparisons)	
Is_WinEVT-Deident-Elastic_output.conf	Import deidentified JSONL files, apply ECS field mapping were applicable and output to Elasticsearch	
Logstash Support Inputs		
Grok-seld-custom-ecs.txt	Custom regular expression patterns used for Linux event parsing	
winlogbeat-decodexml.yml	Custom settings for the Winlogbeat agent software including the changes required to for XML output	
Data Testing Utilities		
testdatadeident.sh	<p>A production workflow shell script that accepts two inputs: list of sensitive terms such as domain names, IP ranges machine prefixes, accounts</p> <p>the deidentified data file to be checked for sensitive terms</p> <p>Searches entire file for each term, prints out count of records observed and SHA256 hash value of the file for tracking data custody</p> <p>Deidentified data can be search for detected sensitive terms and release decision made</p>	seldproject_sensitiveterms.txt <i>deidentified-data-file</i>
winevt_drops.sh	Development utility to confirm no record loss is occurring in the pipeline, important for	

	validating control dataset pipeline	
winevt_unprocessed.sh	Development utility to summarize, by event ID, Windows EventLog records collected by the pipeline but not processed via deidentification	

Appendix C Security Investigation Testing

The attack chain term “lateral movement” refers to the steps a threat agent will take after acquiring access on one or more systems internal within the organization they are attacking (MITRE, 2022b). Detecting this activity can be challenging for an analyst because the threat agent, attempting to avoid detection, often employs the same built-in operating system capabilities that an administrator or advanced computer would be using (SentinalOne, 2020).

This appendix validates which events would be recorded in an intrusion using Windows, Linux, and firewall event data, and what a cyber security analyst may be able to determine using deidentified data. An attack simulation was run to while active systems continued to perform all processes and generate thousands of events which do not pertain to the attack at all. Admittedly this is not an assessment of how effectively an individual security analyst would perform such a task since the attacker and investigator are one. Testing the viability of investigations using deidentified data is work recommended for future phases of this project.

Scenario

A privileged user has been recently compromised but remains undetected within the organization, during a recent off-hours period the contents of a credit card database were stolen. The company has been advised by an authority they may have been the source of a data breach and are now required to investigate. To protect the organizations privacy and reputation an escrow party engaged a third-party forensic company to investigate the incident and provided them with deidentified data covering a 72 hour period the organization suspects was the attack window.

Environment description provided to investigator

The client organization has remote access enabled for the user network; authorized users can connect via RDP to their local workstation. Administrators in the user support group have RDP access to all local workstations to provide support after hours.

The organization’s network topology is as follows: 10.0.0.0/8 is allocated for servers and networking equipment, 172.16.0.0/12 is allocated for user workstations, remote access and voice over IP, 192.168.0.0/16 is allocated for internet services.

Attack Sequence and Investigation

The attack sequence is broken into ten steps, each step is followed by the details of what was observable in the original source data and second section showing both the deidentified data and how a cyber security analyst or investigator may process the data.

1. A compromised account connects into an administrator’s computer via remote access.

Original Observed:

A Logon type 10 from 172.18.40.24 with the username “*gmoyer*” occurred on April 10th, 11:10:30 MDT (Fig. C.1). Note: this IP is an SSH forwarding source within the lab but can be considered remote access for this simulation.

```

dleece@infsec19:/var/tmp$ grep -i moyer winevtls.jsonl-2023-04-10 | grep 4624 | grep '"LogonType": "10"'
{"computer_name": "wkstn153.yymm.local", "process": {"pid": 660, "thread": {"id": 7920}}, "keywords": ["Audit Success"], "level": "information", "channel": "Security", "event_data": {"ProcessName": "C:\\Windows\\System32\\svchost.exe", "LogonGuid": "{F326c545-25ad-c596-5413-03def93f0715}", "TargetOutboundDomainName": "-", "VirtualAccount": "%1843", "IpPort": "0", "TransmittedServices": "-", "LmPackageName": "-", "RestrictedAdminMode": "%1843", "ElevatedToken": "%1843", "WorkstationName": "WKSTN153", "SubjectDomainName": "YMMV", "LogonProcessName": "User32", "TargetDomainName": "YMMV", "LogonType": "10", "SubjectLogonId": "0x3e7", "TargetOutboundUserName": "-", "KeyLength": "0", "TargetLogonId": "0x14b8e35", "SubjectUserName": "WKSTN153", "TargetLinkedLogonId": "0x0", "IpAddress": "172.18.40.24", "ImpersonationLevel": "%1833", "TargetUserName": "gmoyer", "ProcessId": "0x5d8", "SubjectUserSid": "S-1-5-18", "TargetUserSid": "S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1111", "AuthenticationPackageName": "Negotiate", "opcode": "Info", "version": 2, "record_id": 6042, "event_id": "4624", "task": "Logon", "provider_guid": "{54849625-5478-4994-a5ba-3e3b0328c30d}", "activity_id": "{45552086-6b0b-0000-1f21-55450b6bd901}", "time_created": "2023-04-10T17:10:30.277Z", "provider_name": "Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing", "outcome": "success"}

```

Figure C.1 RDP logon event starting the attack

Deidentified Observed:

Twenty Windows Logon type 10 events collected from 3 different source addresses are observable, two are in the 172.27 network, one source IP (Fig. C.2). 172.27.235.209 does not have any external traffic, therefore the analyst may consider this the remote access server (Fig. C.3, Fig. C.4).

Figure C.2 RDP Login search to identify remote access

Figure C.3 Validation steps to filter workstations from remote access

Figure C.4 Confirmation of no external access attempts

2. From an internal workstation the attacker makes a connection to a second workstation.

Original Observed:

Logon type 10 from 172.18.40.153, connecting to WKSTN250 with the account “moyer-priv” in the target username field, 11:26:48 (Fig. C.5)

```

{"computer_name":"wkstn250.ymmv.local","process":{"pid":680,"thread":{"id":9152}},"keywords":["Audit_Success"],"level":"information","channel":"Security","event_data":{"ProcessName":"C:\\Windows\\System32\\svchost.exe","LogonGuid":{"440e702a-6fcb-feaa-8507-613b814beb8e"},"TargetOutboundDomainName":"-","VirtualAccount":{"1843"},"IpPort":0,"TransmittedServices":"-","LmPackageName":"-","RestrictedAdminMode":{"1843},"ElevatedToken":{"1842},"WorkstationName":"WKSTN250","SubjectDomainName":"YMMV","TargetDomainName":"YMMV","LogonProcessName":"User32","LogonType":10,"SubjectLogonId":"0x3e7","TargetOutboundUserName":"","KeyLength":0,"TargetLogonId":"0x1cd20dd","SubjectUserName":"WKSTN250","TargetLinkedLogonId":"0x1cd2305","IpAddress":"172.18.40.153","ImpersonationLevel":{"1833},"TargetUserName":"moyer-priv","ProcessId":"0x4b4","SubjectUserSid":"S-1-5-18","TargetUserSid":"S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162","AuthenticationPackageName":"Negotiate"},"opcode":"info","version":2,"record_id":43903,"event_id":4624,"task":"Logon","provider_guid":{"54849625-5478-4994-a5ba-3e3b0328c30d"},"activity_id":{"aceea579-69ec-0000-0ba6-eeacec69d901},"time_created":2023-04-10T17:26:48.953Z,"provider_name":"Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing","outcome":"success"}

```

Figure C.5 Second RDP logon

Deidentified Observed:

Only three Logon type 10 events occurred from the suspected remote access IP 172.27.235.209, to two different workstations, “Dqrt3hs-“ and “5Suf3XGz“ (Fig. C.6).

Figure C.6 Narrowing the RDP search using source IP

To confirm the theory that the compromised account first connected in via remote access then connected to a second system, the source IP address of each workstation needs to be identified something not captured in a 4624-logon-type-10 event. Modifying the search settings reveals “Dqrt3hs-“ uses IP address 172.27.235.82, something that can be correlated by workstation account name “Dqry3hs-\$” connecting to two domain controllers at regular intervals (Fig. C.7). Due to the nature of encryption, “WKSTN123” and “wkstn123” are completely different values, unfortunately within Windows Event Log records the computer name can appear in either case depending on the event and field value. An analyst understanding this potential for two pseudonyms would then add the workstation name “qNOXyebT” to the investigation artifact list.

Figure C.7 Wildcard pseudonym search to find related artifacts

Limiting the search to source address 172.27.235.82 shows 4 different workstations were accessed within the investigation window. In large environments the number of unique workstation targets could be 400, far too many to individually investigate, therefore other indicators need to be considered. Reviewing the cluster of events on April 9th, the solitary April 10th event could potentially be an afterhours login, something often occurring in insider threat scenarios which is a possibility the analyst must consider.

Figure C.8 Cluster analysis of RDP login events

Workstation “vbzMnfy” is also associated with the Windows computer name “PisDK7IX.Mf-9.Y6Xsg” which reported a type 10 authentication with the account name “R9f2Wx7CL7”. Repeating the workstation search above IP address 172.27.235.179 can also be associated with this host. It is worth noting that in addition to logon events, Kerberos ticket granting events also record the IP address. Since the SELD deidentification modules pseudonymize the appearance of IP addresses in all fields the message field can also be used for searching (Fig. C9).

Figure C.9 Locating the source IP using Kerberos event

3. Opening a command line as an administrative user.

Original Observed:

Process monitoring and command line auditing have been enabled on all workstations, recording the user opening a command prompt with administrative privileges. A command line shell with elevated privileges was opened by the account "moyer-priv" at 11:34:36 MDT Microsoft does recommend monitoring of "TokenElevationType 1937" performed by real user accounts as potentially suspicious activity (Microsoft, 2022a).

```
{ "computer_name": "wkstn250.ymmv.local", "process": { "pid": 4, "thread": { "id": 4872 } }, "keywords": [ "Audit Success" ], "level": "information", "channel": "Security", "event_data": { "MandatoryLabel": "S-1-16-12288", "ParentProcessName": "C:\\windows\\explorer.exe", "NewProcessId": "0x74c", "TokenElevationType": "%1937", "NewProcessName": "C:\\windows\\system32\\cmd.exe", "SubjectLogonId": "0x3e7", "TargetLogonId": "0x1cd20dd", "CommandLine": "C:\\WINDOWS\\system32\\cmd.exe", "SubjectUserName": "WKSTN250$", "SubjectDomainName": "YMMV", "TargetUserName": "moyer-priv", "ProcessId": "0x1608", "TargetDomainName": "YMMV", "SubjectUserSid": "S-1-5-18", "TargetUserSid": "S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162", "message": "A new process has been created.\\n\\nCreator Subject:\\n\\tSecurity ID:\\t\\TS-1-5-18\\n\\tAccount Name:\\t\\TWKSTN250$\\n\\tAccount Domain:\\t\\YMMV\\n\\tLogon ID:\\t\\t0x3E7\\n\\nTarget Subject:\\n\\tSecurity ID:\\t\\TS-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162\\n\\tAccount Name:\\t\\moyer-priv\\n\\tAccount Domain:\\t\\YMMV\\n\\tLogon ID:\\t\\t0x1CD20DD\\n\\nProcess Information:\\n\\tNew Process ID:\\t\\t0x74c\\n\\nNew Process Name:\\tC:\\windows\\system32\\cmd.exe\\n\\tToken Elevation Type:\\t%1937\\n\\tMandatory Label:\\t\\TS-1-16-12288\\n\\tCreator Process ID:\\t0x1608\\n\\tCreator Process Name:\\tC:\\windows\\explorer.exe\\n\\tProcess Command Line:\\t\\C:\\WINDOWS\\system32\\cmd.exe\\n\\nToken Elevation Type indicates the type of token that was assigned to the new process in accordance with User Account Control policy.\\n\\nType 1 is a full token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. A full token is only used if User Account Control is disabled or if the user is the built-in Administrator account or a service account.\\n\\nType 2 is an elevated token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. An elevated token is used when User Account Control is enabled and the user chooses to start the program using Run as administrator. An elevated token is also used when an application is configured to always require administrative privilege or to always require maximum privilege, and the user is a member of the Administrators group.\\n\\nType 3 is a limited token with administrative privileges removed and administrative groups disabled. The limited token is used when User Account Control is enabled, the application does not require administrative privilege, and the user does not choose to start the program using Run as administrator. ", "opcode": "Info", "version": 2, "record_id": 44043, "event_id": "4688", "task": "Process Creation", "provider_guid": "{54849625-5478-4994-a5ba-3e3b0328c30d}", "time_created": "2023-04-10T17:34:36.461Z", "provider_name": "Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing", "outcome": "success" }
```

Figure C.10 Windows event 4688 tracking privilege use

Deidentified Observed:

Figure C.11 shows 18,993 processes were reported from this single workstation in a 72-hour period, there is one event of interest, and the analyst has nothing to go on beyond the assumption an administrative account may have been used.

Figure C.11 Process execution events from workstation under investigation

The token elevation type is an extracted field that can be used to begin reducing the event volume. Removing token elevation number 1936, which is associated with internal system processes instantly reduces the search set to 2,081 records. Within those records only three non-system users have been observed, and the account associated with the RDP login “R9f2Wx7cL7” is at the top of the list (Fig. C.12).

Figure C.12 Process creation grouped by observed accounts

Filtering by the username of interest reduces the event set to 696, filtering by token elevation type 1937 further reduces the record set to just 27, one of which is the elevated command shell initiated at 11:34:36 (Fig. C.13)

Figure C.13 Additional filtering by suspected account and high privilege token

4. Searching for any files that contain the strings “passwd”, “cred” or “database”

Original Observed:

The “moyer-priv” account uses a built-in Windows utility “findstr” to search for files with strings listed above at 11:41:04 (Fig. C.14). It is worth noting the output redirection to a text file is missing so it is not clear this action is malicious from Windows event captured. A quick review of figure C.15 leaves less doubt about threat agent intentions.

```
["computer_name":"wkstn250.yymm.local","process":{"pid":4,"thread":{"id":5884},"keywords":["Audit_Success"],"level":"information","channel":"Security","event_data":{"MandatoryLabel":"S-1-16-12288","ParentProcessName":"C:\\Windows\\System32\\cmd.exe","NewProcessId":"0x1a48","TokenElevationType":"%1937","NewProcessName":"C:\\Windows\\System32\\findstr.exe","SubjectLogonId":"0x1cd20dd","TargetLogonId":"0x0","CommandLine":"findstr /spin \"passwd cred database\" *.*","SubjectUserName":"moyer-priv","SubjectDomainName":"YMMV","TargetUserName":"-","ProcessId":"0x74c","TargetDomainName":"-","SubjectUserSid":"S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162","TargetUserSid":"S-1-0-0"},"message":"A new process has been created.\\n\\nCreator Subject:\\n\\nSecurity ID:\\t\\tS-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162\\n\\nAccount Name:\\t\\tmoyer-priv\\n\\nAccount Domain:\\t\\tYMMV\\n\\nLogon ID:\\t\\t0x1CD20DD\\n\\nTarget Subject:\\n\\nSecurity ID:\\t\\tS-1-0-0\\n\\nAccount Name:\\t\\t-\\n\\nAccount Domain:\\t\\t-\\n\\nLogon ID:\\t\\t0x0\\n\\nProcess Information:\\n\\nNew Process ID:\\t\\t0x1a48\\n\\nNew Process Name:\\t\\tC:\\Windows\\System32\\findstr.exe\\n\\nToken Elevation Type:\\t\\t%1937\\n\\nMandatory Label:\\t\\tS-1-16-12288\\n\\nCreator Process ID:\\t\\t0x74c\\n\\nCreator Process Name:\\t\\tC:\\Windows\\System32\\cmd.exe\\n\\nProcess Command Line:\\t\\tfindstr /spin \"passwd cred database\" *.*\\n\\nToken Elevation Type indicates the type of token that was assigned to the new process in accordance with User Account Control policy.\\n\\nType 1 is a full token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. A full token is only used if User Account Control is disabled or if the user is the built-in Administrator account or a service account.\\n\\nType 2 is an elevated token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. An elevated token is used when User Account Control is enabled and the user chooses to start the program using Run as administrator. An elevated token is also used when an application is configured to always require administrative privilege or to always require maximum privilege, and the user is a member of the Administrators group.\\n\\nType 3 is a limited token with administrative privileges removed and administrative groups disabled. The limited token is used when User Account Control is enabled, the application does not require administrative privilege, and the user does not choose to start the program using Run as administrator."},"opcode":"Info","version":2,"record_id":44055,"event_id":4688,"task":"Process Creation","provider_guid":"{54949625-5478-4994-a5ba-3e3b0328c30d}","time_created":"2023-04-10T17:41:04.059Z","provider_name":"Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing","outcome":"success"}]
```

Figure C.14 Searching with “findstr” from an elevated command prompt

Figure C.15 Screen shot of actual command executed

Deidentified Observed:

With a potential start time the suspicious activity, the analyst removes the subject username filter, increasing visible events to include processes without a subject username. The document search action is now visible and traceable back to the elevated command prompt (Fig. C.16). Searching for documents with administrative privileges will allow documents not owned by the elevated user to also be examined.

Figure C.16 Deidentified data view, searching from elevated command prompt

- Notepad.exe was used to review a document within a few minutes of a second search command looking for text document content was started.

Original Observed:

The account "moyer-priv" used notepad.exe to open a file called `c:\temp\credsearch.txt` at 12:53:10 MDT (Fig. C.17). Reviewing the command line arguments, the most likely reason for this action would appear to be searching for credentials, although is only an assumption. A cyber security analyst does not have the actual screen content shown in Figure C.18, nor is this type of data something most organizations would be capable of collecting.

```

dieece@infoc19:/var/tmp$ grep -i notepad winevtlogs-2023-04-10
{"computer_name":"wkatn250.yymm.local","process":{"pid":4,"thread":{"id":4632},"keywords":["Audit Success"],"level":"information","channel":"Security","event_data":{"MandatoryLabel":"S-1-16-8192","ParentProcessName":"C:\\Windows\\explorer.exe","NewProcessId":"0x2044","TokenElevationType":"%1938","NewProcessName":"C:\\Windows\\System32\\notepad.exe","SubjectLogonId":"0x1cd2305","TargetLogonId":"0x0","CommandLine":"C:\\WINDOWS\\system32\\NOTEPAD.EXE" C:\\temp\\credsearch.txt","SubjectUserName":"moyer-priv","SubjectDomainName":"YMMV","TargetUserName":"","ProcessId":"0x1608","TargetDomainName":"","SubjectUserSid":"S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162","TargetUserSid":"S-1-0-0"},"message":"A new process has been created.\n\nCreator Subject:\n\nSecurity ID:\t\tS-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162\n\nAccount Name:\t\tmoyer-priv\n\nAccount Domain:\t\tYMMV\n\nLogon ID:\t\t0x1CD2305\n\nTarget Subject:\n\nSecurity ID:\t\tS-1-0-0\n\nAccount Name:\t\t\n\nAccount Domain:\t\t\n\nLogon ID:\t\t0x0\n\nProcess Information:\n\nNew Process ID:\t\t0x2044\n\nNew Process Name:\t\tC:\\Windows\\System32\\notepad.exe\n\nToken Elevation Type:\t\t%1938\n\nMandatory Label:\t\tS-1-16-8192\n\nCreator Process ID:\t\t0x1608\n\nCreator Process Name:\t\tC:\\Windows\\explorer.exe\n\nProcess Command Line:\t\t\"C:\\WINDOWS\\system32\\NOTEPAD.EXE\" C:\\temp\\credsearch.txt\n\nToken Elevation Type indicates the type of token that was assigned to the new process in accordance with User Account Control policy.\n\nType 1 is a full token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. A full token is only used if User Account Control is disabled or if the user is the built-in Administrator account or a service account.\n\nType 2 is an elevated token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. An elevated token is used when User Account Control is enabled and the user chooses to start the program using Run as administrator. An elevated token is also used when an application is configured to always require administrative privilege or to always require maximum privilege, and the user does not choose to start the program using Run as administrator.","opcode":"Info","version":2,"record_id":44166,"event_id":4688,"task":"Process Creation","provider_guid":{"54849625-5478-4994-a5ba-3e3b0328c30d},"time_created":"2023-04-10T18:53:10.997Z","provider_name":"Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing","outcome":"success"}

```

Figure C.17 Privileged account opening the search output file

6. Unauthorized access to protected data via privilege abuse.

Original Observed:

Notepad.exe was used to open a second document at 12:58:46 MDT, using the account “moyer-priv” and the path to the document was “c:\users\sbaig\Documents”. The mismatch between account names “moyer-priv” and “sbaig” is consistent with a privileged account accessing a document owned by a different user. Like the step 5 example, event collection does not tell the entire story, part of the skill set of an experienced cyber analyst is the ability to validate mental models using only the abstracted view provided by cyber event data.

```
[{"computer_name": "wkstn250.ymmv.local", "process": {"pid": 4, "thread": [{"id": 5884}], "keywords": ["Audit Success"], "level": "information", "channel": "Security", "event_data": {"MandatoryLabel": "S-1-16-8192", "ParentProcessName": "C:\\Windows\\explorer.exe", "NewProcessId": "0x1598", "TokenElevationType": "1938", "NewProcessName": "C:\\Windows\\System32\\notepad.exe", "SubjectLogonId": "0xcd2305", "TargetLogonId": "0x0", "CommandLine": "C:\\WINDOWS\\system32\\NOTEPAD.EXE C:\\Users\\sbaig\\Documents\\POS\\YMMV_POS-Details.txt", "SubjectUserName": "moyer-priv", "SubjectDomainName": "YMMV", "TargetUserName": "-", "ProcessId": "0x1608", "TargetDomainName": "-", "SubjectUserSid": "S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162", "TargetUserSid": "S-1-0-0"}, "message": "A new process has been created.\n\nCreator Subject:\n\nSecurity ID:\t\tS-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162\n\nAccount Name:\t\tmoyer-priv\n\nAccount Domain:\t\tYMMV\n\nLogon ID:\t\t0xcd2305\n\nTarget Subject:\n\nSecurity ID:\t\tS-1-0-0\n\nAccount Name:\t\t-\n\nAccount Domain:\t\t-\n\nLogon ID:\t\t0x0\n\nProcess Information:\n\nNew Process ID:\t\t0x1598\n\nProcess Name:\t\tC:\\Windows\\System32\\notepad.exe\n\nToken Elevation Type:\t\t1938\n\nMandatory Label:\t\tS-1-16-8192\n\nCreator Process ID:\t\t0x1608\n\nCreator Process Name:\t\tC:\\Windows\\explorer.exe\n\nProcess Command Line:\t\t\"C:\\WINDOWS\\system32\\NOTEPAD.EXE\" C:\\Users\\sbaig\\Documents\\POS\\YMMV_POS-Details.txt\n\nToken Elevation Type indicates the type of token that was assigned to the new process in accordance with User Account Control policy.\n\nType 1 is a full token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. A full token is only used if User Account Control is disabled or if the user is the built-in Administrator account or a service account.\n\nType 2 is an elevated token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. An elevated token is used when User Account Control is enabled and the user chooses to start the program using Run as administrator. An elevated token is also used when an application is configured to always require administrative privilege or to always require maximum privilege, and the user is a member of the Administrators group.\n\nType 3 is a limited token with administrative privileges removed and administrative groups disabled. The limited token is used when User Account Control is enabled, the application does not require administrative privilege, and the user does not choose to start the program using Run as administrator."}, "opcode": "Info", "version": 2, "record_id": 44177, "event_id": "4688", "task": "Process Creation", "provider_guid": "54849625-5478-4994-a5ba-3e3b0328c30d", "time_created": "2023-04-10T18:58:46.910Z", "provider_name": "Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing", "outcome": "success"}
```

Figure C.20 Suspicious document read

Although some readers may challenge the idea that a person would store credentials in a text document, it does occur because they are the only ones with access because it was saved to their local document directory (C.21). The content in the document looks like notes an administrator might make for themselves taking on a new role. Application configuration files are also known to contain passwords, IP addresses as well as authentication keys and local copies may occasionally be found on an administrator’s workstation. A class of malware known as information stealers was developed to take advantage of this all-too-common oversight (Sheridan, 2022).

Figure C.21 Screen shot of credential leak example

Deidentified Observed:

Excluding many processes executing on the workstation, include several background events associated to the user account “R9f2Wx7cL7” reduces the search set back down to 48 events. Figure C.22 is a strong indicator that the threat agent has located a document in another user directory and is reviewing it in notepad. Actions recorded after this may provide an indication of the threat agent’s next move.

Figure C.22 Deidentified view unauthorized document access

- A connection is attempted to a Linux database server from the internal Windows workstation.

Original Observed:

A process called putty.exe was started at 12:59:39 MDT by the account “moyer-priv”. This executable is most commonly the widely used free SSH client for Windows but event 4688 only reports the execution of the file, it does not validate legitimacy.

```

{"computer_name": "wkstn250.yymm.vl0cal", "process": {"pid": 4, "thread": {"id": 448}}, "keywords": ["Audit Success"], "level": "information", "channel": "Security", "event_data": {"MandatoryLabel": "S-1-16-8192", "ParentProcessName": "C:\\Windows\\explorer.exe", "NewProcessId": "0xc34", "TokenElevationType": "%1938", "NewProcessName": "C:\\appdev\\sshclients\\putty.exe", "SubjectLogonId": "0xcd2305", "TargetLogonId": "0x0", "CommandLine": "C:\\appdev\\sshclients\\putty.exe", "SubjectUserName": "moyer-priv", "SubjectDomainName": "YMMV", "TargetUserName": "-", "ProcessId": "0x1608", "TargetDomainName": "-", "SubjectUserSid": "S-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162", "TargetUserSid": "S-1-0-0"}, "message": "A new process has been created.\n\nCreator Subject:\n\nSecurity ID:\t\tS-1-5-21-2346142638-329485983-1959203885-1162\n\nAccount Name:\t\tmoyer-priv\n\nAccount Domain:\t\tYMMV\n\nLogon ID:\t\t0xcd2305\n\nTarget Subject:\n\nSecurity ID:\t\tS-1-0-0\n\nAccount Name:\t\t-\n\nAccount Domain:\t\t-\n\nLogon ID:\t\t0x0\n\nProcess Information:\n\nNew Process ID:\t\t0xc34\n\nNew Process Name:\t\tC:\\appdev\\sshclients\\putty.exe\n\nToken Elevation Type:\t\t%1938\n\nMandatory Label:\t\tS-1-16-8192\n\nCreator Process ID:\t\t0x1608\n\nCreator Process Name:\t\tC:\\Windows\\explorer.exe\n\nProcess Command Line:\t\t\"C:\\appdev\\sshclients\\putty.exe\" \n\nToken Elevation Type indicates the type of token that was assigned to the new process in accordance with User Account Control policy.\n\nType 1 is a full token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. A full token is only used if User Account Control is disabled or if the user is the built-in Administrator account or a service account.\n\nType 2 is an elevated token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. An elevated token is used when User Account Control is enabled and the user chooses to start the program using Run as administrator. An elevated token is also used when an application is configured to always require administrative privilege or to always require maximum privilege, and the user is a member of the Administrators group.\n\nType 3 is a limited token with administrative privileges removed and administrative groups disabled. The limited token is used when User Account Control is enabled, the application does not require administrative privilege, and the user does not choose to start the program using Run as administrator.", "opcode": "info", "version": 2, "record_id": 44182, "event_id": "4688", "task": "Process Creation", "provider_guid": "{54849625-5478-4994-a5ba-3e3b0328c30d}", "time_created": "2023-04-10T18:59:39.587Z", "provider_name": "Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing", "outcome": "success"}

```

Figure C.23 SSH client initiation

Deidentified Observed:

A process called putty.exe was started at 12:59:39 MDT by the account “R9f2Wx7cL7”. Since the parent process is the Windows operating system user shell and the process owner is “R9f2Wx7cL7” that is the account that almost certainly launched the file believed to be an SSH client.

Figure C.24 Deidentified view SSH client process

- Logon attempts are made to Linux servers from the workstation IP.

Original Observed:

A failed and an accepted SSH login even occurred starting at 13:01:54 MDT using the account “ecomadmin” from IP 172.18.40.250 which was associated with the second Windows workstation in step 2 of the investigation.

```
<85>Apr 10 13:01:54 infdev19 sshd[102588]: pam_unix(sshd:auth): authentication failure; logname= uid=0 euid=0
tty=ssh ruser= rhost=172.18.40.250 user=ecomadmin
<38>Apr 10 13:01:56 infdev19 sshd[102588]: Failed password for ecomadmin from 172.18.40.250 port 60249 ssh2
<38>Apr 10 13:02:36 infdev19 sshd[102734]: Accepted password for ecomadmin from 172.18.40.250 port 60259 ssh2
```

Figure C.25 SSH login events from Windows workstation

Deidentified Observed:

The cyber security analyst observing the use of an SSH client would understand any login activity would be recorded by the SSH daemon on the servers the threat agent attempted or succeeded logging into. Since the analyst also knows the IP address of the workstation executing the SSH client process this search returns very useful information immediately (Fig. C.26).

Figure C.26 Deidentified view SSH login events

The user actions on April 9th look authorized because the account name used is the same account name observed in the directory path to the document the analyst is presuming contained credentials. The occurrence of multiple login events over a twenty-minute period is also consistent with regular authorized interaction; the April 10th events are occurring within one minute and are using an account not seen previously (Fig. C.27).

Figure C.27 Deidentified view of authorized and unauthorized SSH login events

9. The threat agent explores the Linux server looking for database content.

Original Observed:

After the successful login at 13:02:56 MDT no further action is recorded for the “ecoadmin” user until 14:31:27. At that time a recursive find command is used to search for any file with “.sql” in the name and the process is being run as “root”, via the “sudo” command so the ecoadmin account was either privileged elevated their privileges to the top administrative level on a Linux or UNIX server.

```
linux3164.log-2023-04-10:<85>Apr 10 13:01:54 infdev19 sshd[102588]: pam_unix(sshd:auth): authentication failure; logname= uid=0 euid=0 tty=ssh ruser= rhost=172.18.40.250 user=ecoadmin
linux3164.log-2023-04-10:<38>Apr 10 13:01:56 infdev19 sshd[102588]: Failed password for ecoadmin from 172.18.40.250 port 60249 ssh2
linux3164.log-2023-04-10:<38>Apr 10 13:02:36 infdev19 sshd[102734]: Accepted password for ecoadmin from 172.18.40.250 port 60259 ssh2
linux3164.log-2023-04-10:<86>Apr 10 13:02:36 infdev19 sshd[102734]: pam_unix(sshd:session): session opened for user ecoadmin by (uid=0)
linux3164.log-2023-04-10:<86>Apr 10 13:02:36 infdev19 systemd: pam_unix(systemd-user:session): session opened for user ecoadmin by (uid=0)
linux3164.log-2023-04-10:<85>Apr 10 14:31:27 infdev19 sudo: ecoadmin : TTY=pts/0 ; PWD=/ ; USER=root ; COMMAND=/usr/bin/find / -name *.sql*
linux3164.log-2023-04-10:<86>Apr 10 14:31:27 infdev19 sudo: pam_unix(sudo:session): session opened for user root by ecoadmin(uid=0)
linux3164.log-2023-04-11:<86>Apr 11 17:53:07 infdev19 sshd[102734]: pam_unix(sshd:session): session closed for user ecoadmin
```

Figure C.28 Linux activity reported to auth facility

Unlike Windows command line, auditing non-privileged shell actions on Linux is not done with the auth facility. Any activities between the time of known login, the single “sudo” command and the “ssh” session end at April 11th 11:53:07 are not knowable in this remote log collection configuration although forensic evidence may still exist on the server itself. Figure XX captures

the preliminary events performed by the threat agent. Although information is disclosed through the utility script that informs the threat agent of what to look for, the holder of the “*ecomadmin*” account had an expectation that only authorized entities would be accessing the script.

Figure C.29 Screen shot Linux recon with compromised account

Deidentified Observed:

The cyber security analyst searching through the deidentified data will observe the exact same sequence of events with the IP addresses, server hostname and account name changed. Once again, the investigation is stalled unless the analyst considers the mental model of a threat agent willing to connect to multiple machines, search for and presumably steal data. If data was found by the threat agent, the common next step is sending the data outside the organization, a reasonable presumption since a data breach was reported by an external party.

Figure C.30 Deidentified view Linux activity captured by auth facility

10. The threat agent uses the Linux secure copy SCP command to send the stolen data outside the organization.

Original Observed:

The perimeter firewall recorded all outbound traffic events, but the cyber analyst has no idea how long the search took to complete or if any data was found. The one logical assumption that can be made traffic prior the threat agent login event can be deemed unrelated and destination addresses ruled out of the investigation. Figure C.31 shows a search and filtering approach to summarize all outbound traffic from the server network over a 1-hour period.

```
dleece@infdev28:/opt/seld/rawlogs/analyzed$ grep '2023-04-10T14:' fwsyslog.log-2023-04-10 | grep '10.\.30.\.30' | awk -F ' ' '{print $19,$22}' | sort -nr | uniq -c
12 10.20.30.72 123
1 10.20.30.6 80
22 10.20.30.6 53
2 10.20.30.6 443
3 10.20.30.63 123
1 10.20.30.56 80
2 10.20.30.56 443
4 10.20.30.38 53
1 10.20.30.38 443
1 10.20.30.38 22
4 10.20.30.38 123
2 10.20.30.28 53
1 10.20.30.28 443
3 10.20.30.28 123
4 10.20.30.24 123
2 10.20.30.209 80
72 10.20.30.209 53
3 10.20.30.209 443
3 10.20.30.209 123
1 10.20.30.133 80
2 10.20.30.133 443
```

Figure C.31 Firewall log summary via command line

The 154 records are still too much to investigate manually, therefore filtering of previous traffic was used to narrow down the source IP to 10.20.0.38.

Deidentified Observed:

Filtering by 10.0.0.0/8 reduced the event volume 90%, removing the destination address range of 192.168.0.0/16 and starting the search after 14:30 MDT reduces the search to 10 just 10 events from 6 sources (Fig. C.32).

Figure C.32 Source analysis filtering in firewall logs

Four of the six sources shown in figure C.32 were communicating with destination IP addresses owned by Microsoft and eliminated because the cyber analyst knows the source would be a Linux server. Four outbound requests are observable from the two IP sources and three of those requests are outbound HTTPS. Although HTTPS can be used for file transfer, two of the IP addresses are assigned to Canonical, the company managing the Ubuntu Linux distribution,

Figure C.33 Linux firewall traffic analysis

Conversly, the outbound TCP port 22 event at 14:42 is consistent with a secure copy file transfer and the destination IP address 23.227.163.178 is assigned to a company that provides low-cost virtual private servers (Fig. C.34).

— Quick Stats	
IP Location	United States Seattle Nodisto It
ASN	AS29802 HVC-AS, US (registered May 08, 2003)
Whois Server	whois.arin.net
IP Address	23.227.163.178

NetRange:	23.227.160.0 - 23.227.191.255
CIDR:	23.227.160.0/19
NetName:	NET-23-227-160-0-19
NetHandle:	NET-23-227-160-0-1
Parent:	NET23 (NET-23-0-0-0-0)
NetType:	Direct Allocation
OriginAS:	AS29802
Organization:	HIVELOCITY, Inc. (HVC-3)
RegDate:	2013-09-23
Updated:	2022-05-13
Comment:	https://www.hivelocity.net
Comment:	For abuse related issues email abuse@hivelocity.net
Ref:	https://rdap.arin.net/registry/ip/23.227.160.0

Figure C.34 Whois lookup for suspect destination IP

Intrusion Detection Analysis

The recording the threat agent's actions was representing in the deidentified data set as well, although some assumptions were made about the conclusions a cyber security analyst would make, efforts were made within each deidentified view section to illustrate the logical linkage between each movement. Presumably the investigator would share the key deidentified artifacts like host machines observed, account names, event sequence and times. The source organization would then reidentify these artifacts and validate the findings by looking through their own data. It should also be appreciated that even within the original source data the trail of actions and filtering required is far from obvious.

The events within this example are a composite of various cyber intrusions the author has responded to in the past ten years, and examples of each activity can be found in almost any data breach report.

Appendix D Event Field Selection & Deidentification

Event parsing has been the most time-consuming portion of this and many other projects that must analyze, process, and potentially enrich large numbers of cyber event records. Although security luminary Dr. Anton Chuvakin’s 2009 opensource SEIM prediction appears to be holding (Chukavin, 2009), products like Elastic manage to walk the commercial support line while making quality software available to researchers for free (Elastic, 2023c). Additionally, the SIGMA rules initiative seems to have garnered community support, likely because of the commitment to interoperability (Patzke, 2023).

The initial public code release of SELD includes many parsing rules, configurations that drop events or tag them for further processing, and it became quickly apparent the defining criteria for identification and tracking its implementation would be critical to ensure reliable deidentification.

Note: table D1 originally appears in chapter three of this thesis and is included below for reference and convenience.

Table D1 Event element deidentification summary

Field Context	Details or Examples	Sensitive quasi-identifier
Event Type	Login, account change, firewall block, service stop	Potentially*
Event time	Time and date reported by OS, firewall, application	No
Event Location	Source and destination systems, IP addresses, geo-location meta data,	Yes
Event Source	Program or process responsible for event	Potentially**
Event Outcome	Success or failure status of the action	No
Entity identity	Account names, system host names, file location names	Yes

* Only events that include an account or group name that could be associated with an individual person, EG. The command “usermod jbeck” could be a reidentifier but “usermod root” would not

** If the process name includes meta-data traceable to a user or organization, EG. loginshell-jbeck could be a reidentifier but bash would not

Table D.2 documents the current list of Windows Event IDs processed by the deidentification pipeline that contain at least one data value defined as sensitive by the criteria outlined in table D.1. Twenty-six unique field names have been identified during the research project, many of which are the same data type, such as a SID, but identified by a different name such as TargetSid, TargetUserSid, or SubjectUserSid depending on what that data value represents in a specific message. Custom Ruby modules were created for each data type observed during research and development, and typically multiple field names can be deidentified with the same Ruby module. This reuse approach moves much of the conditional logic into the Logstash

pipeline configuration, using its ability to quickly identify fields within an event to direct the event toward one of more of the Ruby modules needed to deidentify the field values.

As new Windows Event IDs are selected for additional security or observability monitoring new field names may need to be added to the tracking table shown below, and in the event a new data structure is observed a new Ruby module may need to be created. During the project, the decision to include process creation and command line auditing uncovered the need for a new module specifically for deidentifying the path structures in the three fields provided by that event record.

Table D.2 Windows Event Log Deidentification Fields

Original Field Name	Associated Event ID	Ruby Module
Computer	4624, 4648, 4625, 4672, 4688, 4769, 4768, 4770, 5140, 4771, 4647, 4776, 1100, 4724, 4732, 4104	hostname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.CommandLine	4688	cmduserdata_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.IpAddress	4624, 4648, 4625, 4769, 4768, 4770, 5140, 4771	ip64port_deident-winevt-v2.rb
Event_data.IpPort	4624, 4648, 4625, 4769, 4768, 4770, 5140, 4771	ip64port_deident-winevt-v2.rb
Event_data.MemberName	4732	groupmodify_deident-winevt.rb
Event_data.MemberSid	4732	groupmodify_deident-winevt.rb
Event_data.NewProcessName	4688	cmduserdata_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.ParentProcessName	4688	cmduserdata_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.SamAccountName		acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.ShareName	5140	
Event_data.ServiceName	4769, 4768, 4770, 4771	acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.ServiceSid	4769, 4768, 4770	sid_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.SubjectDomainName	4624, 4648, 4625, 4672, 4688, 5140, 4724, 4732	domname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.SubjectUserName	4624, 4648, 4625, 4672, 4688, 5140, 4724, 4732	acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.SubjectUserSid	4624, 4648, 4625, 4672, 4688, 5140, 4724, 4732	sid_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.TargetDomainName	4624, 4648, 4625, 4688, 4769, 4768, 4770, 4647, 4732	domname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.TargetInfo	4648	acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.TargetOutboundDomainName	4624	
Event_data.TargetOutboundUserName	4624	acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.TargetServerName	4648	acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.TargetSid	4768, 4771, 4724	sid_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb

Event_data.TargetUserName	4624, 4648, 4625, 4688, 4769, 4768, 4770, 4771, 4647, 4776, 4724, 4732	acctname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.TargetUserSid	4624, 4625, 4688, 4647	sid_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.Workstation	4776	hostname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
Event_data.WorkStationName	4624, 4625	hostname_deident-winevt_ecs-v2.rb
message	4648, 4625, 4672, 4688, 4769, 4768, 4770, 5140, 4647, 4776	msg_sans-format-v2.rb

The Linux authlog records the program name generating the record and the remainder of the message requires regular expression parsing and extraction. Table D.3 lists the programs generating the events followed by a list of fields that were observed, unfortunately the authlog approach doesn't have unique identifiers like the Windows event log channel so message parsing for new events is still expected to be a requirement.

Table D.3 Linux authlog observed sensitive fields by program

Program Name	Sensitive Field Data	Ruby Module
sudo	Sudo user, target user, uid, filepath, ruser, hostname	filepath_deident.rb multiuser_deident.rb ip_port_name_deident_ecs-v1.rb
su	Sudo user, target user, hostname	multiuser_deident.rb name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
sshd	Username,sourceip, sourceport, hostname	ip_port_name_deident_ecs-v1.rb
unix_chkpwd	Username, hostname	name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
system-logind	Username, hostname	name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
login	Username, hostname	name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
systemd	Username, hostname	name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
passwd	Username, hostname	name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
useradd	Username, groupname, hostname	multiuser_deident.rb name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
usermod	Username, groupname, hostname	multiuser_deident.rb name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
groupadd	Username, groupname, hostname	multiuser_deident.rb name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
groupmod	Username, groupname, hostname	multiuser_deident.rb name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
chage	Username, hostname	name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
chfn	Username, hostname	name_only_deident_ecs-v1.rb
CRON	No fields identified to date	
polkitd	Drop message, no security value	

The PFSense firewall used for the project only used the firewall traffic features, none of the VPN or web content filtering capabilities were implemented. Due to the single log source type only one Ruby module was required. The `ip_port_name_deident-pfsf.rb` deidentifies the hostname of the firewall sending the logs as well as the source or destination IP addresses if they are within one of the three RFC1918 ranges. The source port is also deidentified to avoid attackers attempting reidentification through timing and source port monitoring. Although this is not perceived as a serious threat unless public data sharing is considered, building the capability in at the start seemed prudent.

Appendix E Re-Identification Risk Assessment

This risk assessment will use the Factor Analysis of Information Risk (FAIR) model (Fig. E.1) and taxonomy (Freund & Jones, 2015) for determining an organization's residual risk exposure resulting from sharing cyber event data deidentified with a software-based approach such as the solution presented by the SELD project.

Figure E.1 FAIR Ontology & Taxonomy - single page view (McCoy, 2017)

The threat community for this risk assessment has been limited to two threat agents, defined below, in the scenario where the threat actor gains access to the deidentified data files created by the original data owner (ODO) and stored at the location of a third-party data processor (3DP).

The first threat agent, encountering the deidentified data may be willing to perform analysis outside the previously agreed upon analysis platform or limitations negotiated with the ODO such as overlaying patterns or sequences against other public data sources or comparing deidentified data from other contributors. Privacy researchers often use the term “honest but curious” (HBC) to define such entities and from the risk analysis perspective proceeding outside the bounds of a data-sharing agreement should be considered adversarial. (Paverd et al., 2014) redefine the HBC threat actor with characteristics the SELD project presumes align with 3DP most likely to have potential access to deidentified cyber event data generated by an external organization. I.E., although willing to “bend-the-rules” in search of greater data insights an HBC 3DP would not be expected to directly attack the organization they believe they have reidentified to confirm research findings.

“The honest-but-curious (HBC) adversary is a legitimate participant in a communication protocol who will not deviate from the defined protocol but will attempt to learn all possible information from legitimately received messages.” (Paverd et al., 2014)

The second threat agent considered is a cyber-criminal or military actor attacking the 3DP and gaining access to systems and data within that organization. Presumably deidentified cyber event data would be just one of the many types of data stored within a research facility and the threat actor may have no knowledge of the existence function or source of such data. A second presumption is being made that there is limited public awareness of the ODO relationship with 3DP although the nature of public private partnerships such as a post-secondary institution collaboration with industry does often result in some public visibility which may have led to targeting that organization or individual within the organization.

Impact assessment

Loss assessment will be limited to actual and potential losses due to reidentification that could be experienced by the original data owner. Since the deidentified data was created from original data already collected within the organization the loss experienced would be the potential confidentiality of the information within the data set. Financial losses would only materialize if the deidentified data were able to be used to disclose Personally Identifiable Information (PII) or if the data was strategic to a successful cyber-attack against the organization.

Secondary losses due to PII exposure will not be considered because direct identifiers are not normally included within cyber event logs. It is highly unlikely that deidentified cyber event data would include such content unless a significant error was made by the ODO during the event data field selection and analysis SELD framework phase. As a result, the only data likely to be exposed would be a subset of the organization’s cyber event data collected during a point in time with sensitive fields deidentified using encryption and shift ciphers.

If the encrypted data was able to be decrypted, the threat agent would have some of the IP addresses, host names and account names of cyber systems that were active within an organization during the time of collection, they may not actually be able to identify the original source organization or area within that organization. Within the cyberattack sequence or chain, successfully decrypting the deidentified data has resulted in information similar to that collected during the system discovery phases of an attack (MITRE, 2022a), without the benefit of initial access or guarantees of current data or collection completeness. Acknowledging that any such attack must first be predicated by the attacker bypassing the organization’s existing perimeter, the loss magnitude would be within the range of existing cyber risks the organization.

The requirement to gain unauthorized access to an organization’s networks or applications to take advantage of the reidentified information removes the HBC threat agent from the remaining assessment work. The HBC may reveal either portions of the deidentified, or reidentified data in their research, at which point the encryption keys used to initially create the deidentified data could demonstrate the ODO source and allow consequence enforcement for data-sharing agreement violation.

Threat Event Frequency

The FAIR model breaks more nebulous or contentious probabilities into smaller measurable elements to improve probability estimation ranges. The first consideration in this scenario is the criminal or military threat agent must identify and compromise a 3DP and locate the deidentified

data within the organization. In 2022, the Verizon Data Breach Report listed only 1,241 incidents, 282 resulting in data disclosure events with 75% of the threat agents considered external(Verizon Business, 2023). Global estimates of post-secondary institutions range from 80-100,000 (Usher & Williams, 2022); presuming 10% of those institutions are publically known for research the probability the 3DP chosen by the ODO is successfully attacked over the next year and data will be exposed is $4.3 * 10^{-6}$.

Despite the extremely low probability, some organizations have very low residual risk tolerance for certain types of data exposure. Therefore, a second consideration can be added to the risk analysis, the reidentification resistance created through the encryption of sensitive fields.

Vulnerability

All computer host and account names are encrypted using FF3 format preserving encryption, recognized by NIST as providing provable 128-bit encryption when properly implemented (Dworkin, 2019). Crypto analysts reporting flaws in FF3 FPE encryption were testing 6-digit pins in a 10-character alphabet, (Durak & Vaudenay, 2017; Hoang et al., 2019) versus 64 characters used for host and account names, 16 times the minimum possible input character requirement.

IP address deidentification relies on two shift ciphers moving the network and host portions of the IP address different distances from the original and potentially different directions. The rotation model may suggest the famous Enigma machine code cracking actions which took as little as 20 minutes using 1940's technology (Furness, 2021). The IP shift cipher is not vulnerable to the same type of attack because unlike human speech there is no requirement to use IP addresses in a specific sequence or range, as a result, without at least some original IP addresses being included in the data there is no means for the threat agent to validate the correct cipher settings. Additionally, each organization can use any network within the RFC1918 assigned allocations, therefore an attacker successfully guessing both shift cipher settings would have no ability to validate which organization the network was deployed.

The SELD processing workflow includes a final step to remove sensitive terms like known IP ranges from the data, should the ODO make a processing mistake a small percentage of the data, (less than 0.62% worst case during testing), may include original IP addresses in non-standard locations such as the supplemental message text of Windows events. Accounting for such a mistake, the probability of clear text and its equivalent cipher text being visible in the same record can be considered 1% – 4%. The variable we cannot estimate is how many threat agents would have the capability or desire to launch a cryptographic attack against a dataset that is still 96%-99% encrypted, therefore a 50% probability is assigned.

Table E.1 FAIR probability Calculations

Post-secondary Type	Threat Event Frequency	Reidentification Vulnerability	Loss Event Frequency	Internal Access Success
all	0.0155		0.00282	
research	0.00155 * 0.000282	0.04 * 0.5	$8.742 * 10^{-8}$	0.30

Table E.1 captures the probabilities discussed in the threat event frequency and vulnerability sections and it is worth noting that from the ODO perspective a threat event has only occurred once the 3DP has been attacked and the deidentified data is in the possession of the criminal or military threat agent. A loss event, cyber event data confidentiality in this scenario, only occurs once the threat agent defeats the encryption. It could also be argued that until the threat agent successfully uses that information in a successful cyber-attack no loss has occurred. Giving the threat agent a 30% chance of gaining access still results in risk realization probabilities well below any meaningful percentage.

Risk mitigation recommendations

- Limit data sharing to vetted researchers or research institutions, ensure they have active cyber security programs in place.
- Define data-sharing agreements between ODO and 3DP.
- Use different encryption keysets for each 3DP allowing attribution of source should deidentified data become public.
 - Do not share encryption keys with 3DP.
 - Maintain strict controls within ODO to protect encryption keys (Article 29 Working Party, 2014).
- Maintain a log of deidentified data shared with each 3DP.
- Limit the original data inputs to portions of the organization's environment, EG., 7 days of traffic logs from 30% of the firewalls may be adequate, 30 days from 100% may not be necessary for research and expose more data.

Future Work

The shift cipher algorithm works as intended but more analysis and tests to identify the time required to brute force keys using known cipher text attacks. Additionally, a mechanism to additionally modify IP values using a second shifting table, like the Enigma plug wire approach, may further complicate the reliable reidentification of IP addresses.

Risk Assessment Assumption Testing

The following example is based on a three-day data set collected from the SELD project lab, during that time multiple changes were made to computer accounts and hosts. Each of the internal network computers had internet access and one system exposed the SFTP/SSH service to the internet. During this time an attack simulating a threat agent gaining access to a key administrator's account was performed to validate analyst search capability with a complex attack path, resulting in one record being exposed.

Figure E.2 shows a summary of the deidentified data set, 335,527 cyber event records in total.

Figure E.2 Three-day test dataset from unknown organization

Figure E.3 illustrates the outcome of an ODO not noticing the exposure of a sensitive term, considering it meaningful to 3DP analysis or not considering it adequate context to support reidentification.

Figure E.3 Single record selection due to known keyword.

Analysis

Internet searching for the terms “YMMV” and “POS” returned more than a million results, far more than any threat agent would likely be willing to filter through without additional details within the record to narrow down the searching scope. The complete contents of the individual deidentified cyber event records are included below. Green highlighting indicates fields that were encrypted, and the yellow highlights show the occurrence of both clear and cipher text in the same record. At this point the attacker will still need to try every possible decryption key against the string “PKMt” until it returns the string “YMMV”.

Recent estimates on how long such an attack could take (Tobias, 2021) are still millions of years but cryptography does fail and the FPE implementation used was recertified by NIST in 2019 after flaws were discovered in the original FF3 algorithm (Dworkin, 2019). Decryption of the deidentified data should therefore be considered possible but disproportionate with the value gained, greatly reducing the likelihood the threat agent will act.

```

computer_name:PisDK7IX.Mf-9.Y6Xsg
process{2}
  pid:4
  thread{1}
    id:5884
keywords[1]
  0:Audit Success
level:information
channel:Security
event_data{15}
  MandatoryLabel:S-1-16-8192

```

ParentProcessName:C:\\Windows\\explorer.exe
NewProcessId:0x1598
TokenElevationType:%%1938
NewProcessName:C:\\Windows\\System32\\notepad.exe
SubjectLogonId:0x1cd2305
TargetLogonId:0x0
CommandLine:"C:\\WINDOWS\\system32\\NOTEPAD.EXE\"
C:\\Users\\PMOQL\\Documents\\POS\\YMMV_POS-Details.txt
SubjectUserName:R9f2Wx7cL7
SubjectDomainName:PKMt
TargetUserName:-
ProcessId:0x1608
TargetDomainName:-
SubjectUserSid:S-1-5-21-0334535618-953786910-8880575821-111108
TargetUserSid:S-1-0-0

opcode:Info

message:A new process has been created. Creator Subject: Security ID: S-1-5-21-0334535618-953786910-8880575821-111108 Account Name: R9f2Wx7cL7 Account Domain: PKMt Logon ID: 0x1CD2305 Target Subject: Security ID: S-1-0-0 Account Name: - Account Domain: - Logon ID: 0x0 Process Information: New Process ID: 0x1598 New Process Name: C:\\Windows\\System32\\notepad.exe Token Elevation Type: %%1938 Mandatory Label: S-1-16-8192 Creator Process ID: 0x1608 Creator Process Name: C:\\Windows\\explorer.exe Process Command Line: \"C:\\WINDOWS\\system32\\NOTEPAD.EXE\" C:\\Users\\PMOQL\\Documents\\POS\\PKMt_POS-Details.txt Token Elevation Type indicates the type of token that was assigned to the new process in accordance with User Account Control policy. Type 1 is a full token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. A full token is only used if User Account Control is disabled or if the user is the built-in Administrator account or a service account. Type 2 is an elevated token with no privileges removed or groups disabled. An elevated token is used when User Account Control is enabled and the user chooses to start the program using Run as administrator. An elevated token is also used when an application is configured to always require administrative privilege or to always require maximum privilege, and the user is a member of the Administrators group. Type 3 is a limited token with administrative privileges removed and administrative groups disabled. The limited token is used when User Account Control is enabled, the application does not require administrative privilege, and the user does not choose to start the program using Run as administrator.

version:2

record_id:44177

task:Process Creation
event_id:4688
provider_guid:{54849625-5478-4994-a5ba-3e3b0328c30d}
time_created:2023-04-10T18:58:46.910Z
provider_name:Microsoft-Windows-Security-Auditing
outcome:success

Appendix F Reidentification within Shared Data

IP Host reidentification attack

Figure F.1 shows how a third-party data processor(3DP) reidentification attack can be performed within a deidentified dataset. Starting at the bottom of the record set, at 17:59:41.343 an external IP connects to 192.168.41.202 on port 22, the default TCP port for the Secure Shell daemon (SSHD). The sequence of records shows an external IP address, 170.106.117.160 connecting to an internal address of 192.168.41.202 at 17:59:41.343, an event recorded by the project lab’s firewall. At 17:59:43 the SSHD process is reporting failed authentication attempts from this same external IP, therefore the hostname tEx0lm-FA can be logically associated with the IP address 192.168.41.202.

Since this dataset was deidentified using the SELD software, the 3DP has only linked one pseudonym to another which maintains the privacy of the original records. Additionally, due to the global use of RFC1918 IP addresses, host IP 192.168.41.202 is no more attributable to an individual organization than the true address 192.168.40.59. The realistic possibility of the same Ip range being observed in several organizations around the world aligns with the k-anonymity privacy treatment also recommended for deidentified data (EDPB, 2020) .

Although not typically personally identifiable, most organizations consider IP addressing of internal computers confidential. Therefore, testing the data privacy against a standard like GDPR, which acknowledges electronic information as a quasi-identifier, could be considered adequate in the absence of any regulatory standard specifically defining the requirements for deidentifying cyber event data.

Figure F.1 Reidentification within record set